

Most Cited Papers in Software Engineering 2013-2023

Martin Monperrus
KTH Royal Institute of Technology
monperrus@kth.se

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Abstract

This compilation presents a list of the most cited research papers in software engineering from 2013 to 2023, published in leading academic venues. By leveraging APIs from CrossRef and Semantic Scholar, we systematically gather and rank influential works based on citation metrics, providing a valuable resource for researchers, educators, and industry professionals to understand the field. This document can also serve for individuals to strengthen their academic credits with impact facts. Full bibliometric data is accessible in the accompanying repository.

1 Introduction

I aim at compiling influential research articles that have significantly impacted the field of software engineering, based on citation metrics. Such a compilation highlights both seminal works and the important topics the community is working on at a given point in time.

This compilation has important usages. Researchers may use it to steer their research. Educators can incorporate these seminal works into their curriculum development and teaching. Students know where to focus their reading. Additionally, industry professionals might prioritize these papers to stay updated on notable results, ultimately fostering a more informed and effective software engineering progress.

Also, this independent and objective list of influential papers can serve as a powerful tool for individuals looking to strengthen their applications or promotion materials. By emphasizing on their key noted works, they can demonstrate their impact, sharpening their academic profile. This hopefully contributes to a meritocratic, data-driven academic system.

Methodology. To create this document, I follow a systematic protocol using APIs from CrossRef and Semantic Scholar. First, I select the venues based on the top-10 of the automated [ranking of Google Scholar](#) for software research ¹. Then, I use the CrossRef API to retrieve a comprehensive list of papers published in each year. Once the list of papers per venue and per year is collected, we utilize the Semantic Scholar API to gather citation data for each paper. This involves sending requests to the Semantic Scholar API with the unique identifier (DOI)

¹International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE), IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering (TSE), Journal of Systems and Software (JSS), Information and Software Technology (IST), Empirical Software Engineering (EmSE), Symposium on the Foundations of Software Engineering (FSE), International Conference on Automated Software Engineering (ASE), ACM Transactions on Software Engineering and Methodology (TOSEM)

of the papers obtained from CrossRef. This API returns a reliable citation counts. Other sources, such as Google Scholar, do not provide such programmatic access. While they may give different citation metrics, the order of magnitude is expected to be the same and the ranking to be stable over different bibliometrics sources. Finally, a script aggregates this data and computes the list of most cited papers in Software Engineering, presented below.

Format. In the presentation of the results, I decide to only give the order of the papers based on citation counts rather than providing the exact citation numbers, which is changing too fast. I restrict this document to the top-10 most cited papers per venue. I do not filter anything; non-technical papers, such as reviews, and editorials are kept, if they are most cited. I give the raw factual bibliometrics results, it's left to the reader to interpret their meaning. The full data, incl. exact citation counts, is available in the appendix repository at <https://github.com/monperrus/most-cited-se-papers>. The data has been collected in January 2025.

Discussion. Finally, I note that the nature of impact in scientific research is multifaceted and is not captured by citation counts alone. Here, it only serves as a computable proxy for influence. While high citation rates may suggest a paper's visibility within the academic community, they do not necessarily reflect the true significance or novelty of the work. For example, it is widely accepted that surveys are often much cited yet could not be considered as seminal. Also, there are seminal contributions with low citation metrics. To fully understand the impact of a piece of research, it is essential to adopt a nuanced perspective that considers the specific ways in which a study has shaped subsequent work in both academia and industry, as well as its broader implications for society.

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2 Related Work

Several studies have previously examined highly-cited papers in the field of software engineering. Garousi and Fernandes [1] provided a comprehensive analysis of the highly-cited papers in software engineering at publication time. Similarly, Wohlin [4] conducted an analysis of the most cited articles in software engineering journals, focusing on the trends and patterns in citation metrics up to that point in time. Additionally, Garousi and Mäntylä [3] explored the relationship between citations, research topics, and active countries in software engineering, offering insights into the global landscape of research in this domain. Finally, Garousi and Fernandes [2] investigated the balance between the quantity and impact of software engineering papers, providing a perspective on the field's publication trends.

While these studies have made significant contributions to understanding citation patterns in software engineering, they are now outdated, and they do not reflect the recent years of research in software engineering. The rapid evolution of software engineering research necessitates an updated compilation of influential papers that captures the current state of the discipline. This paper fills that gap by systematically collecting and analyzing citation data from leading venues in software engineering in period 2013-2023, thereby providing a fresh perspective on the most impactful works in the field.

3 Most cited papers

2013 35th International Conference on Software Engineering

1. [Expectations, outcomes, and challenges of modern code review](#) (Alberto Bacchelli, Christian Bird)
2. [SemFix: Program repair via semantic analysis](#) (Hoang Duong Thien Nguyen, Dawei Qi, Abhik Roychoudhury, Satish Chandra)
3. [Why don't software developers use static analysis tools to find bugs?](#) (Brittany Johnson, Yoonki Song, Emerson Murphy-Hill, Robert Bowdidge)
4. [Transfer defect learning](#) (Jaechang Nam, Sinno Jialin Pan, Sunghun Kim)
5. [It's not a bug, it's a feature: How misclassification impacts bug prediction](#) (Kim Herzig, Sascha Just, Andreas Zeller)
6. [Boa: A language and infrastructure for analyzing ultra-large-scale software repositories](#) (Robert Dyer, Hoan Anh Nguyen, Hriday Rajan, Tien N. Nguyen)
7. [RERAN: Timing- and touch-sensitive record and replay for Android](#) (Lorenzo Gomez, Iulian Neamtiu, Tanzirul Azim, Todd Millstein)
8. [Analysis of user comments: An approach for software requirements evolution](#) (Laura V. Galvis Carreno, Kristina Winbladh)
9. [How, and why, process metrics are better](#) (Foyzur Rahman, Premkumar Devanbu)
10. [How to effectively use topic models for software engineering tasks? An approach based on Genetic Algorithms](#) (Annibale Panichella, Bogdan Dit, Rocco Oliveto, Massimiliano Di Penta, Denys Poshyanyk, Andrea De Lucia)

IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering 2013

1. [A large-scale empirical study of just-in-time quality assurance](#) (Yasutaka Kamei, Emad Shihab, Bram Adams, Ahmed E. Hassan, Audris Mockus, Anand Sinha, Naoyasu Ubayashi)
2. [Whole Test Suite Generation](#) (Gordon Fraser, Andrea Arcuri)
3. [Data Quality: Some Comments on the NASA Software Defect Datasets](#) (Martin Sheperd, Qinbao Song, Zhongbin Sun, Carolyn Mair)
4. [Software Architecture Optimization Methods: A Systematic Literature Review](#) (Aldeida Aleti, Barbora Buhnova, Lars Grunske, Anne Koziolok, Indika Meedeniya)
5. [What Industry Needs from Architectural Languages: A Survey](#) (Ivano Malavolta, Patricia Lago, Henry Muccini, Patrizio Pelliccione, Antony Tang)
6. [Quantifying the Effect of Code Smells on Maintenance Effort](#) (Dag I.K. Sjoberg, Aiko Yamashita, Bente C.D. Anda, Audris Mockus, Tore Dyba)

7. [Self-Organizing Roles on Agile Software Development Teams](#) (Rashina Hoda, James Noble, Stuart Marshall)
8. [Local versus Global Lessons for Defect Prediction and Effort Estimation](#) (Tim Menzies, Andrew Butcher, David Cok, Andrian Marcus, Lucas Layman, Forrest Shull, Burak Turhan, Thomas Zimmermann)
9. [Featured Transition Systems: Foundations for Verifying Variability-Intensive Systems and Their Application to LTL Model Checking](#) (Andreas Classen, Maxime Cordy, Pierre-Yves Schobbens, Patrick Heymans, Axel Legay, Jean-Francois Raskin)
10. [Reducing Features to Improve Code Change-Based Bug Prediction](#) (S. Shivaji, E. James Whitehead, R. Akella, Sunghun Kim)

Journal of Systems and Software 2013

1. [An orchestrated survey of methodologies for automated software test case generation](#) (Saswat Anand, Edmund K. Burke, Tsong Yueh Chen, John Clark, Myra B. Cohen, Wolfgang Grieskamp, Mark Harman, Mary Jean Harrold, Phil McMinn, Antonia Bertolino, J. Jenny Li, Hong Zhu)
2. [Software ecosystems – A systematic literature review](#) (Konstantinos Manikas, Klaus Marius Hansen)
3. [An exploration of technical debt](#) (Edith Tom, Aybüke Aurum, Richard Vidgen)
4. [Cloud computing security: The scientific challenge, and a survey of solutions](#) (Mark D. Ryan)
5. [Towards innovation measurement in the software industry](#) (Henry Edison, Nauman bin Ali, Richard Torkar)
6. [On the reliability of mapping studies in software engineering](#) (Claes Wohlin, Per Runeson, Paulo Anselmo da Mota Silveira Neto, Emelie Engström, Ivan do Carmo Machado, Eduardo Santana de Almeida)
7. [Agile requirements prioritization in large-scale outsourced system projects: An empirical study](#) (Maya Daneva, Egbert van der Veen, Chintan Amrit, Smita Ghaisas, Klaas Sikkell, Ramesh Kumar, Nirav Ajmeri, Uday Ramteerthkar, Roel Wieringa)
8. [A survey of software testing practices in Canada](#) (Vahid Garousi, Junji Zhi)
9. [A high capacity lossless data hiding scheme for JPEG images](#) (Kan Wang, Zhe-Ming Lu, Yong-Jian Hu)
10. [A robust blind color image watermarking in quaternion Fourier transform domain](#) (Xiangyang Wang, Chun-peng Wang, Hong-ying Yang, Pan-pan Niu)

Information and Software Technology 2013

1. [A systematic review of systematic review process research in software engineering](#) (Barbara Kitchenham, Pearl Brereton)
2. [Software fault prediction metrics: A systematic literature review](#) (Danijel Radjenović, Marjan Heričko, Richard Torkar, Aleš Živkovič)
3. [Software clone detection: A systematic review](#) (Dhavleesh Rattan, Rajesh Bhatia, Maninder Singh)
4. [Systematic literature reviews in software engineering](#) (Claes Wohlin, Rafael Prikladnicki)
5. [Graphical user interface \(GUI\) testing: Systematic mapping and repository](#) (Ishan Banerjee, Bao Nguyen, Vahid Garousi, Atif Memon)
6. [Interpretative case studies on agile team productivity and management](#) (Claudia de O. Melo, Daniela S. Cruzes, Fabio Kon, Reidar Conradi)
7. [Acquiring and sharing tacit knowledge in software development teams: An empirical study](#) (Sharon Ryan, Rory V. O'Connor)
8. [Scalable prediction of non-functional properties in software product lines: Footprint and memory consumption](#) (Norbert Siegmund, Marko Rosenmüller, Christian Kästner, Paolo G. Giarrusso, Sven Apel, Sergiy S. Kolesnikov)
9. [Systematic reviews in software engineering: An empirical investigation](#) (He Zhang, Muhammad Ali Babar)
10. [Empirical evaluation of the effects of mixed project data on learning defect predictors](#) (Burak Turhan, Ayşe Tosun Mısırlı, Ayşe Bener)

Empirical Software Engineering 2013

1. [A practical guide to controlled experiments of software engineering tools with human participants](#) (Andrew J. Ko, Thomas D. LaToza, Margaret M. Burnett)
2. [Bug characteristics in open source software](#) (Lin Tan, Chen Liu, Zhenmin Li, Xuanhui Wang, Yuanyuan Zhou, Chengxiang Zhai)
3. [Mining software repair models for reasoning on the search space of automated program fixing](#) (Matias Martinez, Martin Monperrus)
4. [Recovering from a decade: a systematic mapping of information retrieval approaches to software traceability](#) (Markus Borg, Per Runeson, Anders Ardö)
5. [Understanding the Influence of User Participation and Involvement on System Success – a Systematic Mapping Study](#) (Ulrike Abelein, Barbara Paech)
6. [Measuring and modeling programming experience](#) (Janet Siegmund, Christian Kästner, Jörg Liebig, Sven Apel, Stefan Hanenberg)

7. [Challenges and practices in aligning requirements with verification and validation: a case study of six companies](#) (Elizabeth Bjarnason, Per Runeson, Markus Borg, Michael Unterkalmsteiner, Emelie Engström, Björn Regnell, Giedre Sabaliauskaite, Annabella Loconsole, Tony Gorschek, Robert Feldt)
8. [Automating extract class refactoring: an improved method and its evaluation](#) (Gabriele Bavota, Andrea De Lucia, Andrian Marcus, Rocco Oliveto)
9. [Agile vs. structured distributed software development: A case study](#) (Hans-Christian Estler, Martin Nordio, Carlo A. Furia, Bertrand Meyer, Johannes Schneider)
10. [Replications of software engineering experiments](#) (Jeffrey C. Carver, Natalia Juristo, Maria Teresa Baldassarre, Sira Vegas)

Proceedings of the 2013 9th Joint Meeting on Foundations of Software Engineering

1. [Dynodroid: an input generation system for Android apps](#) (Aravind Machiry, Rohan Tahiliani, Mayur Naik)
2. [Convergent contemporary software peer review practices](#) (Peter C. Rigby, Christian Bird)
3. [Jalangi: a selective record-replay and dynamic analysis framework for JavaScript](#) (Koushik Sen, Swaroop Kalasapur, Tasneem Brutch, Simon Gibbs)
4. [API change and fault proneness: a threat to the success of Android apps](#) (Mario Linares-Vásquez, Gabriele Bavota, Carlos Bernal-Cárdenas, Massimiliano Di Penta, Rocco Oliveto, Denys Poshyvanyk)
5. [Z3-str: a z3-based string solver for web application analysis](#) (Yunhui Zheng, Xiangyu Zhang, Vijay Ganesh)
6. [A statistical semantic language model for source code](#) (Tung Thanh Nguyen, Anh Tuan Nguyen, Hoan Anh Nguyen, Tien N. Nguyen)
7. [Diversity in software engineering research](#) (Meiyappan Nagappan, Thomas Zimmermann, Christian Bird)
8. [Scalable analysis of variable software](#) (Jörg Liebig, Alexander von Rhein, Christian Kästner, Sven Apel, Jens Dörre, Christian Lengauer)
9. [Searching for better configurations: a rigorous approach to clone evaluation](#) (Tiantian Wang, Mark Harman, Yue Jia, Jens Krinke)
10. [Understanding gamification mechanisms for software development](#) (Daniel J. Dubois, Giordano Tamburrelli)

2013 28th IEEE/ACM International Conference on Automated Software Engineering

1. [Improving bug localization using structured information retrieval](#) (Ripon K. Saha, Matthew Lease, Sarfraz Khurshid, Dewayne E. Perry)
2. [Leveraging program equivalence for adaptive program repair: Models and first results](#) (Westley Weimer, Zachary P. Fry, Stephanie Forrest)
3. [AutoComment: Mining question and answer sites for automatic comment generation](#) (Edmund Wong, Jinqiu Yang, Lin Tan)
4. [Personalized defect prediction](#) (Tian Jiang, Lin Tan, Sunghun Kim)
5. [Detecting bad smells in source code using change history information](#) (Fabio Palomba, Gabriele Bavota, Massimiliano Di Penta, Rocco Oliveto, Andrea De Lucia, Denys Poshyvanyk)
6. [Variability-aware performance prediction: A statistical learning approach](#) (Jianmei Guo, Krzysztof Czarnecki, Sven Apel, Norbert Siegmund, Andrzej Wasowski)
7. [A comparative analysis of software architecture recovery techniques](#) (Joshua Garcia, Igor Ivkovic, Nenad Medvidovic)
8. [Scalable product line configuration: A straw to break the camel's back](#) (Abdel Salam Sayyad, Joseph Ingram, Tim Menzies, Hany Ammar)
9. [A study of repetitiveness of code changes in software evolution](#) (Hoan Anh Nguyen, Anh Tuan Nguyen, Tung Thanh Nguyen, Tien N. Nguyen, Hridesh Rajan)
10. [OCRA: A tool for checking the refinement of temporal contracts](#) (Alessandro Cimatti, Michele Dorigatti, Stefano Tonetta)

ACM Transactions on Software Engineering and Methodology 2013

1. [A theoretical analysis of the risk evaluation formulas for spectrum-based fault localization](#) (Xiaoyuan Xie, Tsong Yueh Chen, Fei-Ching Kuo, Baowen Xu)
2. [Business Process Model Merging](#) (Marcello La Rosa, Marlon Dumas, Reina Uba, Remco Dijkman)
3. [Achieving scalable model-based testing through test case diversity](#) (Hadi Hemmati, Andrea Arcuri, Lionel Briand)
4. [Facilitating the transition from use case models to analysis models](#) (Tao Yue, Lionel C. Briand, Yvan Labiche)
5. [Personalized Reliability Prediction of Web Services](#) (Zibin Zheng, Michael R. Lyu)
6. [Fault localization prioritization](#) (Shin Yoo, Mark Harman, David Clark)
7. [Portfolio](#) (Collin Mcmillan, Denys Poshyvanyk, Mark Grechanik, Qing Xie, Chen Fu)

8. [Software effort estimation as a multiobjective learning problem](#) (Leandro L. Minku, Xin Yao)
9. [Synthesizing nonanomalous event-based controllers for liveness goals](#) (Nicolás D'ippolito, Victor Braberman, Nir Piterman, Sebastián Uchitel)
10. [An Information Foraging Theory Perspective on Tools for Debugging, Refactoring, and Reuse Tasks](#) (Scott D. Fleming, Chris Scaffidi, David Piorkowski, Margaret Burnett, Rachel Bellamy, Joseph Lawrance, Irwin Kwan)

Proceedings of the 36th International Conference on Software Engineering 2014

1. [An exploratory study of the pull-based software development model](#) (Georgios Gousios, Martin Pinzger, Arie van Deursen)
2. [AR-miner: mining informative reviews for developers from mobile app marketplace](#) (Ning Chen, Jialiu Lin, Steven C. H. Hoi, Xiaokui Xiao, Boshen Zhang)
3. [Coverage is not strongly correlated with test suite effectiveness](#) (Laura Inozemtseva, Reid Holmes)
4. [Checking app behavior against app descriptions](#) (Alessandra Gorla, Ilaria Tavecchia, Florian Gross, Andreas Zeller)
5. [Influence of social and technical factors for evaluating contribution in GitHub](#) (Jason Tsay, Laura Dabbish, James Herbsleb)
6. [The strength of random search on automated program repair](#) (Yuhua Qi, Xiaoguang Mao, Yan Lei, Ziyang Dai, Chengsong Wang)
7. [Achieving accuracy and scalability simultaneously in detecting application clones on Android markets](#) (Kai Chen, Peng Liu, Yingjun Zhang)
8. [Characterizing and detecting performance bugs for smartphone applications](#) (Yepang Liu, Chang Xu, Shing-Chi Cheung)
9. [Using psycho-physiological measures to assess task difficulty in software development](#) (Thomas Fritz, Andrew Begel, Sebastian C. Müller, Serap Yigit-Elliott, Manuela Züger)
10. [Live API documentation](#) (Siddharth Subramanian, Laura Inozemtseva, Reid Holmes)

IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering 2014

1. [Researcher Bias: The Use of Machine Learning in Software Defect Prediction](#) (Martin Shepperd, David Bowes, Tracy Hall)
2. [Predicting Vulnerable Software Components via Text Mining](#) (Riccardo Scandariato, James Walden, Aram Hovsepyan, Wouter Joosen)

3. [Variability in Software Systems—A Systematic Literature Review](#) (Matthias Galster, Danny Weyns, Dan Tofan, Bartosz Michalik, Paris Avgeriou)
4. [Bypassing the Combinatorial Explosion: Using Similarity to Generate and Prioritize T-Wise Test Configurations for Software Product Lines](#) (Christopher Henard, Mike Papadakis, Gilles Perrouin, Jacques Klein, Patrick Heymans, Yves Le Traon)
5. [An Empirical Study of Refactoring Challenges and Benefits at Microsoft](#) (Miryung Kim, Thomas Zimmermann, Nachiappan Nagappan)
6. [How Effectively Does Metamorphic Testing Alleviate the Oracle Problem?](#) (Huai Liu, Fei-Ching Kuo, Dave Towey, Tsong Yueh Chen)
7. [Automatic Summarization of Bug Reports](#) (Sarah Rastkar, Gail C. Murphy, Gabriel Murray)
8. [Overcoming the Equivalent Mutant Problem: A Systematic Literature Review and a Comparative Experiment of Second Order Mutation](#) (Lech Madeyski, Wojciech Orzeszyna, Richard Torkar, Mariusz Jozala)
9. [Methodbook: Recommending Move Method Refactorings via Relational Topic Models](#) (Gabriele Bavota, Rocco Oliveto, Malcom Gethers, Denys Poshyvanyk, Andrea De Lucia)
10. [Test Code Quality and Its Relation to Issue Handling Performance](#) (Dimitrios Athanasiou, Ariadi Nugroho, Joost Visser, Andy Zaidman)

Journal of Systems and Software 2014

1. [Information centric services in Smart Cities](#) (G. Piro, I. Cianci, L.A. Grieco, G. Boggia, P. Camarda)
2. [On the verification of UML/OCL class diagrams using constraint programming](#) (J. Cabot, R. Clarisó, D. Riera)
3. [Modeling continuous integration practice differences in industry software development](#) (Daniel Ståhl, Jan Bosch)
4. [Dynamic adaptation of service compositions with variability models](#) (G.H. Alférez, V. Pelechano, R. Mazo, C. Salinesi, D. Diaz)
5. [Sustainability of Open Source software communities beyond a fork: How and why has the LibreOffice project evolved?](#) (Jonas Gamalielsson, Björn Lundell)
6. [A critical examination of recent industrial surveys on agile method usage](#) (Stavros Stavru)
7. [Slice-based statistical fault localization](#) (Xiaoguang Mao, Yan Lei, Ziyang Dai, Yuhua Qi, Chengsong Wang)
8. [Web application testing: A systematic literature review](#) (Serdar Doğan, Aysu Betin-Can, Vahid Garousi)

9. [A secure Boolean-based multi-secret image sharing scheme](#) (Chien-Chang Chen, Wei-Jie Wu)
10. [Factors that motivate software engineering teams: A four country empirical study](#) (J.M. Verner, M.A. Babar, N. Cerpa, T. Hall, S. Beecham)

Information and Software Technology 2014

1. [A systematic literature review of software requirements prioritization research](#) (Philip Achimugu, Ali Selamat, Roliana Ibrahim, Mohd Naz'ri Mahrin)
2. [Software development in startup companies: A systematic mapping study](#) (Nicolò Patermoster, Carmine Giardino, Michael Unterkalmsteiner, Tony Gorschek, Pekka Abrahamsson)
3. [MoDisco: A model driven reverse engineering framework](#) (Hugo Brunelière, Jordi Cabot, Grégoire Dupé, Frédéric Madiot)
4. [Risks and risk mitigation in global software development: A tertiary study](#) (J.M. Verner, O.P. Brereton, B.A. Kitchenham, M. Turner, M. Niazi)
5. [Communities of practice in a large distributed agile software development organization – Case Ericsson](#) (Maria Paasivaara, Casper Lassenius)
6. [Measuring the health of open source software ecosystems: Beyond the scope of project health](#) (Slinger Jansen)
7. [On strategies for testing software product lines: A systematic literature review](#) (Ivan do Carmo Machado, John D. McGregor, Yguaratã Cerqueira Cavalcanti, Eduardo Santana de Almeida)
8. [Perceived causes of software project failures – An analysis of their relationships](#) (Timo O.A. Lehtinen, Mika V. Mäntylä, Jari Vanhanen, Juha Itkonen, Casper Lassenius)
9. [Testing scientific software: A systematic literature review](#) (Upulee Kanewala, James M. Bieman)
10. [An extended systematic literature review on provision of evidence for safety certification](#) (Sunil Nair, Jose Luis de la Vara, Mehrdad Sabetzadeh, Lionel Briand)

Empirical Software Engineering 2014

1. [Value-cognitive boosting with a support vector machine for cross-project defect prediction](#) (Duksan Ryu, Okjoo Choi, Jongmoon Baik)
2. [Case studies synthesis: a thematic, cross-case, and narrative synthesis worked example](#) (Daniela S. Cruzes, Tore Dybå, Per Runeson, Martin Höst)
3. [Empirical assessment of machine learning-based malware detectors for Android](#) (Kevin Allix, Tegawendé F. Bissyandé, Quentin Jérôme, Jacques Klein, Radu State, Yves Le Traon)

4. [Automated prediction of bug report priority using multi-factor analysis](#) (Yuan Tian, David Lo, Xin Xia, Chengnian Sun)
5. [Exploring the costs of technical debt management – a case study](#) (Yuepu Guo, Rodrigo Oliveira Spínola, Carolyn Seaman)
6. [Empirical evidence on the link between object-oriented measures and external quality attributes: a systematic literature review](#) (Ronald Jabangwe, Jürgen Börstler, Darja Šmite, Claes Wohlin)
7. [Do developers benefit from requirements traceability when evolving and maintaining a software system?](#) (Patrick Mäder, Alexander Egyed)
8. [How product owner teams scale agile methods to large distributed enterprises](#) (Julian M. Bass)
9. [Fostering effective inter-team knowledge sharing in agile software development](#) (Viviane Santos, Alfredo Goldman, Cleidson R. B. de Souza)
10. [Detecting and refactoring code smells in spreadsheet formulas](#) (Felicie Hermans, Martin Pinzger, Arie van Deursen)

Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGSOFT International Symposium on Foundations of Software Engineering 2014

1. [Are mutants a valid substitute for real faults in software testing?](#) (René Just, Darioush Jalali, Laura Inozentseva, Michael D. Ernst, Reid Holmes, Gordon Fraser)
2. [Apposcopy: semantics-based detection of Android malware through static analysis](#) (Yu Feng, Saswat Anand, Isil Dillig, Alex Aiken)
3. [An empirical analysis of flaky tests](#) (Qingzhou Luo, Farah Hariri, Lamyaa Eloussi, Darko Marinov)
4. [Learning natural coding conventions](#) (Miltiadis Allamanis, Earl T. Barr, Christian Bird, Charles Sutton)
5. [A large scale study of programming languages and code quality in github](#) (Baishakhi Ray, Daryl Posnett, Vladimir Filkov, Premkumar Devanbu)
6. [Techniques for improving regression testing in continuous integration development environments](#) (Sebastian Elbaum, Gregg Rothermel, John Penix)
7. [EvoDroid: segmented evolutionary testing of Android apps](#) (Riyadh Mahmood, Nariman Mirzaei, Sam Malek)
8. [Learning to rank relevant files for bug reports using domain knowledge](#) (Xin Ye, Razvan Bunescu, Chang Liu)
9. [On the localness of software](#) (Zhaopeng Tu, Zhendong Su, Premkumar Devanbu)
10. [The plastic surgery hypothesis](#) (Earl T. Barr, Yuriy Brun, Premkumar Devanbu, Mark Harman, Federica Sarro)

Proceedings of the 29th ACM/IEEE International Conference on Automated Software Engineering 2014

1. [Fine-grained and accurate source code differencing](#) (Jean-Rémy Falleri, Floréal Morandat, Xavier Blanc, Matias Martinez, Martin Monperrus)
2. [42 variability bugs in the linux kernel](#) (Iago Abal, Claus Brabrand, Andrzej Wasowski)
3. [Automating regression verification](#) (Dennis Felsing, Sarah Grebing, Vladimir Klebanov, Philipp Rümmer, Mattias Ulbrich)
4. [Search-based inference of polynomial metamorphic relations](#) (Jie Zhang, Junjie Chen, Dan Hao, Yingfei Xiong, Bing Xie, Lu Zhang, Hong Mei)
5. [Recommendation system for software refactoring using innovization and interactive dynamic optimization](#) (Mohamed Wiem Mkaouer, Marouane Kessentini, Slim Bechikh, Kalyanmoy Deb, Mel Ó Cinnéide)
6. [Statistical learning approach for mining API usage mappings for code migration](#) (Anh Tuan Nguyen, Hoan Anh Nguyen, Tung Thanh Nguyen, Tien N. Nguyen)
7. [Leveraging existing tests in automated test generation for web applications](#) (Amin Milani Fard, Mehdi Mirzaaghaei, Ali Mesbah)
8. [Multi-objective optimization in rule-based design space exploration](#) (Hani Abdeen, Dániel Varró, Houari Sahraoui, András Szabolcs Nagy, Csaba Debreceni, Ábel Hegedüs, Ákos Horváth)
9. [Potential biases in bug localization](#) (Pavneet Singh Kochhar, Yuan Tian, David Lo)
10. [Tracking load-time configuration options](#) (Max Lillack, Christian Kästner, Eric Bodden)

ACM Transactions on Software Engineering and Methodology 2014

1. [A Large-Scale Evaluation of Automated Unit Test Generation Using EvoSuite](#) (Gordon Fraser, Andrea Arcuri)
2. [On the Comprehension of Program Comprehension](#) (Walid Maalej, Rebecca Tiarks, Tobias Roehm, Rainer Koschke)
3. [Some Code Smells Have a Significant but Small Effect on Faults](#) (Tracy Hall, Min Zhang, David Bowes, Yi Sun)
4. [When and How to Use Multilevel Modelling](#) (Juan De Lara, Esther Guerra, Jesús Sánchez Cuadrado)
5. [Solving the Search for Source Code](#) (Kathryn T. Stolee, Sebastian Elbaum, Daniel Dobos)
6. [Improving software modularization via automated analysis of latent topics and dependencies](#) (Gabriele Bavota, Malcom Gethers, Rocco Oliveto, Denys Poshyvanyk, Andrea de Lucia)

7. [Peer Review on Open-Source Software Projects](#) (Peter C. Rigby, Daniel M. German, Laura Cowen, Margaret-Anne Storey)
8. [A Unified Test Case Prioritization Approach](#) (Dan Hao, Lingming Zhang, Lu Zhang, Gregg Rothermel, Hong Mei)
9. [Prevalence of coincidental correctness and mitigation of its impact on fault localization](#) (Wes Masri, Rawad Abou Assi)
10. [Code-Smell Detection as a Bilevel Problem](#) (Dilan Sahin, Marouane Kessentini, Slim Bechikh, Kalyanmoy Deb)

2015 IEEE/ACM 37th IEEE International Conference on Software Engineering

1. [IccTA: Detecting Inter-Component Privacy Leaks in Android Apps](#) (Li Li, Alexandre Bartel, Tegawende F. Bissyande, Jacques Klein, Yves Le Traon, Steven Arzt, Siegfried Rasthofer, Eric Bodden, Damien Ocateau, Patrick McDaniel)
2. [Revisiting the Impact of Classification Techniques on the Performance of Defect Prediction Models](#) (Baljinder Ghotra, Shane McIntosh, Ahmed E. Hassan)
3. [Are Students Representatives of Professionals in Software Engineering Experiments?](#) (Iflaah Salman, Ayse Tosun Misirli, Natalia Juristo)
4. [DirectFix: Looking for Simple Program Repairs](#) (Sergey Mechtaev, Jooyong Yi, Abhik Roychoudhury)
5. [Mining Apps for Abnormal Usage of Sensitive Data](#) (Vitalii Avdiienko, Konstantin Kuznetsov, Alessandra Gorla, Andreas Zeller, Steven Arzt, Siegfried Rasthofer, Eric Bodden)
6. [Online Defect Prediction for Imbalanced Data](#) (Ming Tan, Lin Tan, Sashank Dara, Caleb Mayeux)
7. [AppContext: Differentiating Malicious and Benign Mobile App Behaviors Using Context](#) (Wei Yang, Xusheng Xiao, Benjamin Andow, Sihan Li, Tao Xie, William Enck)
8. [Tricorder: Building a Program Analysis Ecosystem](#) (Caitlin Sadowski, Jeffrey Van Gogh, Ciera Jaspan, Emma Soderberg, Collin Winter)
9. [Composite Constant Propagation: Application to Android Inter-Component Communication Analysis](#) (Damien Ocateau, Daniel Luchau, Matthew Dering, Somesh Jha, Patrick McDaniel)
10. [Sustainability Design and Software: The Karlskrona Manifesto](#) (Christoph Becker, Ruzanna Chitchyan, Leticia Duboc, Steve Easterbrook, Birgit Penzenstadler, Norbert Seyff, Colin C. Venters)

IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering 2015

1. [The Oracle Problem in Software Testing: A Survey](#) (Earl T. Barr, Mark Harman, Phil McMinn, Muzammil Shahbaz, Shin Yoo)
2. [The ManyBugs and IntroClass Benchmarks for Automated Repair of C Programs](#) (Claire Le Goues, Neal Holtschulte, Edward K. Smith, Yuriy Brun, Premkumar Devanbu, Stephanie Forrest, Westley Weimer)
3. [Mining Version Histories for Detecting Code Smells](#) (Fabio Palomba, Gabriele Bavota, Massimiliano Di Penta, Rocco Oliveto, Denys Poshyvanyk, Andrea De Lucia)
4. [Investigating Country Differences in Mobile App User Behavior and Challenges for Software Engineering](#) (Soo Ling Lim, Peter J. Bentley, Natalie Kanakam, Fuyuki Ishikawa, Shinichi Honiden)
5. [The Impact of API Change- and Fault-Proneness on the User Ratings of Android Apps](#) (Gabriele Bavota, Mario Linares-Vasquez, Carlos Eduardo Bernal-Cardenas, Massimiliano Di Penta, Rocco Oliveto, Denys Poshyvanyk)
6. [A Survey on Load Testing of Large-Scale Software Systems](#) (Zhen Ming Jiang, Ahmed E. Hassan)
7. [Automated Checking of Conformance to Requirements Templates Using Natural Language Processing](#) (Chetan Arora, Mehrdad Sabetzadeh, Lionel Briand, Frank Zimmer)
8. [COVERT: Compositional Analysis of Android Inter-App Permission Leakage](#) (Hamid Bagheri, Alireza Sadeghi, Joshua Garcia, Sam Malek)
9. [Aligning Qualitative, Real-Time, and Probabilistic Property Specification Patterns Using a Structured English Grammar](#) (Marco Autili, Lars Grunske, Markus Lumpe, Patrizio Pelliccione, Antony Tang)
10. [Improving Multi-Objective Test Case Selection by Injecting Diversity in Genetic Algorithms](#) (Annibale Panichella, Rocco Oliveto, Massimiliano Di Penta, Andrea De Lucia)

Journal of Systems and Software 2015

1. [A systematic mapping study on technical debt and its management](#) (Zengyang Li, Paris Avgeriou, Peng Liang)
2. [Evolution of software in automated production systems: Challenges and research directions](#) (Birgit Vogel-Heuser, Alexander Fay, Ina Schaefer, Matthias Tichy)
3. [Agile methods tailoring – A systematic literature review](#) (Amadeu Silveira Campanelli, Fernando Silva Parreiras)
4. [Health and emergency-care platform for the elderly and disabled people in the Smart City](#) (Aamir Hussain, Rao Wenbi, Aristides Lopes da Silva, Muhammad Nadher, Muhammad Mudhish)

5. [Behavioral software engineering: A definition and systematic literature review](#) (Per Lenberg, Robert Feldt, Lars Göran Wallgren)
6. [An experimental investigation on the innate relationship between quality and refactoring](#) (Gabriele Bavota, Andrea De Lucia, Massimiliano Di Penta, Rocco Oliveto, Fabio Palomba)
7. [Recommender systems based on social networks](#) (Zhoubao Sun, Lixin Han, Wenliang Huang, Xueting Wang, Xiaoqin Zeng, Min Wang, Hong Yan)
8. [Profiling and classifying the behavior of malicious codes](#) (Mamoun Alazab)
9. [Towards energy-efficient scheduling for real-time tasks under uncertain cloud computing environment](#) (Huangke Chen, Xiaomin Zhu, Hui Guo, Jianghan Zhu, Xiao Qin, Jianhong Wu)
10. [Quality of service approaches in cloud computing: A systematic mapping study](#) (Abdelzahir Abdelmaboud, Dayang N.A. Jawawi, Imran Ghani, Abubakar Elsafi, Barbara Kitchenham)

Information and Software Technology 2015

1. [Guidelines for conducting systematic mapping studies in software engineering: An update](#) (Kai Petersen, Sairam Vakkalanka, Ludwik Kuzniarz)
2. [Gamification in software engineering – A systematic mapping](#) (Oscar Pedreira, Félix García, Nieves Brisaboa, Mario Piattini)
3. [Software defect prediction using ensemble learning on selected features](#) (Issam H. Laradji, Mohammad Alshayeb, Lahouari Ghouti)
4. [An empirical study on software defect prediction with a simplified metric set](#) (Peng He, Bing Li, Xiao Liu, Jun Chen, Yutao Ma)
5. [Exploring principles of user-centered agile software development: A literature review](#) (Manuel Brhel, Hendrik Meth, Alexander Maedche, Karl Werder)
6. [A systematic review on the relationship between user involvement and system success](#) (Muneera Bano, Didar Zowghi)
7. [Using metrics in Agile and Lean Software Development – A systematic literature review of industrial studies](#) (Eetu Kupiainen, Mika V. Mäntylä, Juha Itkonen)
8. [A systematic literature review on the barriers faced by newcomers to open source software projects](#) (Igor Steinmacher, Marco Aurelio Graciotto Silva, Marco Aurelio Gerosa, David F. Redmiles)
9. [An empirical analysis of data preprocessing for machine learning-based software cost estimation](#) (Jianglin Huang, Yan-Fu Li, Min Xie)
10. [A systematic literature review on the usage of eye-tracking in software engineering](#) (Zohreh Sharafi, Zéphyrin Soh, Yann-Gaël Guéhéneuc)

Empirical Software Engineering 2015

1. [Comparing and experimenting machine learning techniques for code smell detection](#) (Francesca Arcelli Fontana, Mika V. Mäntylä, Marco Zanoni, Alessandro Marino)
2. [What are mobile developers asking about? A large scale study using stack overflow](#) (Christoffer Rosen, Emad Shihab)
3. [An empirical study of the impact of modern code review practices on software quality](#) (Shane McIntosh, Yasutaka Kamei, Bram Adams, Ahmed E. Hassan)
4. [Analyzing and automatically labelling the types of user issues that are raised in mobile app reviews](#) (Stuart McIlroy, Nasir Ali, Hammad Khalid, Ahmed E. Hassan)
5. [Inferring extended finite state machine models from software executions](#) (Neil Walkinshaw, Ramsay Taylor, John Derrick)
6. [Towards building a universal defect prediction model with rank transformed predictors](#) (Feng Zhang, Audris Mockus, Iman Keivanloo, Ying Zou)
7. [Linguistic antipatterns: what they are and how developers perceive them](#) (Venera Arnaoudova, Massimiliano Di Penta, Giuliano Antoniol)
8. [On the use of many quality attributes for software refactoring: a many-objective search-based software engineering approach](#) (Mohamed Wiem Mkaouer, Marouane Kessentini, Slim Bechikh, Mel Ó Cinnéide, Kalyanmoy Deb)
9. [Open innovation in software engineering: a systematic mapping study](#) (Hussan Munir, Krzysztof Wnuk, Per Runeson)
10. [Preprocessor-based variability in open-source and industrial software systems: An empirical study](#) (Claus Hunsen, Bo Zhang, Janet Siegmund, Christian Kästner, Olaf Leßenich, Martin Becker, Sven Apel)

Proceedings of the 2015 10th Joint Meeting on Foundations of Software Engineering

1. [Suggesting accurate method and class names](#) (Miltiadis Allamanis, Earl T. Barr, Christian Bird, Charles Sutton)
2. [Quality and productivity outcomes relating to continuous integration in GitHub](#) (Bogdan Vasilescu, Yue Yu, Huaimin Wang, Premkumar Devanbu, Vladimir Filkov)
3. [Staged program repair with condition synthesis](#) (Fan Long, Martin Rinard)
4. [Heterogeneous defect prediction](#) (Jaechang Nam, Sunghun Kim)
5. [Is the cure worse than the disease? overfitting in automated program repair](#) (Edward K. Smith, Earl T. Barr, Claire Le Goues, Yuriy Brun)
6. [Performance-influence models for highly configurable systems](#) (Norbert Siegmund, Alexander Grebhahn, Sven Apel, Christian Kästner)

7. [How developers search for code: a case study](#) (Caitlin Sadowski, Kathryn T. Stolee, Sebastian Elbaum)
8. [Measure it? Manage it? Ignore it? software practitioners and technical debt](#) (Neil A. Ernst, Stephany Bellomo, Ipek Ozkaya, Robert L. Nord, Ian Gorton)
9. [Proactive self-adaptation under uncertainty: a probabilistic model checking approach](#) (Gabriel A. Moreno, Javier Cámara, David Garlan, Bradley Schmerl)
10. [Hey, you have given me too many knobs!: understanding and dealing with over-designed configuration in system software](#) (Tianyin Xu, Long Jin, Xuepeng Fan, Yuanyuan Zhou, Shankar Pasupathy, Rukma Talwadker)

2015 30th IEEE/ACM International Conference on Automated Software Engineering

1. [Automated Test Input Generation for Android: Are We There Yet? \(E\)](#) (Shauvik Roy Choudhary, Alessandra Gorla, Alessandro Orso)
2. [Learning to Generate Pseudo-Code from Source Code Using Statistical Machine Translation](#) (Yusuke Oda, Hiroyuki Fudaba, Graham Neubig, Hideaki Hata, Sakriani Sakti, Tomoki Toda, Satoshi Nakamura)
3. [CodeHow: Effective Code Search Based on API Understanding and Extended Boolean Model \(E\)](#) (Fei Lv, Hongyu Zhang, Jian-guang Lou, Shaowei Wang, Dongmei Zhang, Jianjun Zhao)
4. [Do Automatically Generated Unit Tests Find Real Faults? An Empirical Study of Effectiveness and Challenges \(T\)](#) (Sina Shamshiri, Rene Just, Jose Miguel Rojas, Gordon Fraser, Phil McMinn, Andrea Arcuri)
5. [Reverse Engineering Mobile Application User Interfaces with REMAUI \(T\)](#) (Tuan Anh Nguyen, Christoph Csallner)
6. [Combining Deep Learning with Information Retrieval to Localize Buggy Files for Bug Reports \(N\)](#) (An Ngoc Lam, Anh Tuan Nguyen, Hoan Anh Nguyen, Tien N. Nguyen)
7. [Repairing Programs with Semantic Code Search \(T\)](#) (Yalin Ke, Kathryn T. Stolee, Claire Le Goues, Yuriy Brun)
8. [Mining User Opinions in Mobile App Reviews: A Keyword-Based Approach \(T\)](#) (Minh Vu Phong, Tam The Nguyen, Hung Viet Pham, Tung Thanh Nguyen)
9. ["What Parts of Your Apps are Loved by Users?" \(T\)](#) (Xiaodong Gu, Sunghun Kim)
10. [Cost-Efficient Sampling for Performance Prediction of Configurable Systems \(T\)](#) (Atrisha Sarkar, Jianmei Guo, Norbert Siegmund, Sven Apel, Krzysztof Czarnecki)

ACM Transactions on Software Engineering and Methodology 2015

1. [Many-Objective Software Remodularization Using NSGA-III](#) (Wiem Mkaouer, Marouane Kessentini, Adnan Shaout, Patrice Koligheu, Slim Bechikh, Kalyanmoy Deb, Ali Ouni)
2. [A Baseline Model for Software Effort Estimation](#) (Peter A. Whigham, Caitlin A. Owen, Stephen G. Macdonell)
3. [aToucan](#) (Tao Yue, Lionel C. Briand, Yvan Labiche)
4. [Does Automated Unit Test Generation Really Help Software Testers? A Controlled Empirical Study](#) (Gordon Fraser, Matt Staats, Phil McMinn, Andrea Arcuri, Frank Padberg)
5. [Intelligent Code Completion with Bayesian Networks](#) (Sebastian Proksch, Johannes Lerch, Mira Mezini)
6. [Guidelines for Coverage-Based Comparisons of Non-Adequate Test Suites](#) (Milos Gligoric, Alex Groce, Chaoqiang Zhang, Rohan Sharma, Mohammad Amin Alipour, Darko Marinov)
7. [Boa](#) (Robert Dyer, Hoan Anh Nguyen, Hridesh Rajan, Tien N. Nguyen)
8. [Do Automatically Generated Test Cases Make Debugging Easier? An Experimental Assessment of Debugging Effectiveness and Efficiency](#) (Mariano Ceccato, Alessandro Marchetto, Leonardo Mariani, Cu D. Nguyen, Paolo Tonella)
9. [The Effectiveness of Test Coverage Criteria for Relational Database Schema Integrity Constraints](#) (Phil McMinn, Chris J. Wright, Gregory M. Kapfhammer)
10. [Editorial Journal-First Publication for the Software Engineering Community](#) ()

Proceedings of the 38th International Conference on Software Engineering 2016

1. [Automatically learning semantic features for defect prediction](#) (Song Wang, Taiyue Liu, Lin Tan)
2. [Angelix](#) (Sergey Mechtaev, Jooyong Yi, Abhik Roychoudhury)
3. [SourcererCC](#) (Hitesh Sajnani, Vaibhav Saini, Jeffrey Svajlenko, Chanchal K. Roy, Cristina V. Lopes)
4. [Grounded theory in software engineering research](#) (Klaas-Jan Stol, Paul Ralph, Brian Fitzgerald)
5. [Work practices and challenges in pull-based development](#) (Georgios Gousios, Margaret-Anne Storey, Alberto Bacchelli)
6. [Automated parameter optimization of classification techniques for defect prediction models](#) (Chakkrit Tantithamthavorn, Shane McIntosh, Ahmed E. Hassan, Kenichi Matsumoto)

7. [From word embeddings to document similarities for improved information retrieval in software engineering](#) (Xin Ye, Hui Shen, Xiao Ma, Razvan Bunescu, Chang Liu)
8. [Augmenting API documentation with insights from stack overflow](#) (Christoph Treude, Martin P. Robillard)
9. [On the "naturalness" of buggy code](#) (Baishakhi Ray, Vincent Hellendoorn, Saheel Godhane, Zhaopeng Tu, Alberto Bacchelli, Premkumar Devanbu)
10. [Release planning of mobile apps based on user reviews](#) (Lorenzo Villarroel, Gabriele Bavota, Barbara Russo, Rocco Oliveto, Massimiliano Di Penta)

IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering 2016

1. [A Survey on Software Fault Localization](#) (W. Eric Wong, Ruizhi Gao, Yihao Li, Rui Abreu, Franz Wotawa)
2. [A Survey on Metamorphic Testing](#) (Sergio Segura, Gordon Fraser, Ana B. Sanchez, Antonio Ruiz-Cortes)
3. [HYDRA: Massively Compositional Model for Cross-Project Defect Prediction](#) (Xin Xia, David Lo, Sinno Jialin Pan, Nachiappan Nagappan, Xinyu Wang)
4. [Software Development in Startup Companies: The Greenfield Startup Model](#) (Carmine Giardino, Nicolo Paternoster, Michael Unterkalmsteiner, Tony Gorschek, Pekka Abrahamsson)
5. [Automatic Source Code Summarization of Context for Java Methods](#) (Paul W. McBurney, Collin McMillan)
6. [Automatically Recommending Peer Reviewers in Modern Code Review](#) (Motahareh Bahrami Zanjani, Huzefa Kagdi, Christian Bird)
7. [Metamorphic Testing for Software Quality Assessment: A Study of Search Engines](#) (Zhi Quan Zhou, Shaowen Xiang, Tsong Yueh Chen)
8. [Supporting Self-Adaptation via Quantitative Verification and Sensitivity Analysis at Run Time](#) (Antonio Filieri, Giordano Tamburrelli, Carlo Ghezzi)
9. [The Role of Ethnographic Studies in Empirical Software Engineering](#) (Helen Sharp, Yvonne Dittrich, Cleidson R. B. de Souza)
10. [Crossover Designs in Software Engineering Experiments: Benefits and Perils](#) (Sira Vegas, Cecilia Apa, Natalia Juristo)

Journal of Systems and Software 2016

1. [Challenges and success factors for large-scale agile transformations: A systematic literature review](#) (Kim Dikert, Maria Paasivaara, Casper Lassenius)

2. [Teamwork quality and project success in software development: A survey of agile development teams](#) (Yngve Lindsjörn, Dag I.K. Sjøberg, Torgeir Dingsøy, Gunnar R. Bergersen, Tore Dybå)
3. [Revisiting software ecosystems Research: A longitudinal literature study](#) (Konstantinos Manikas)
4. [Multi-level agile project management challenges: A self-organizing team perspective](#) (Rashina Hoda, Latha K. Murugesan)
5. [Engineering context-aware systems and applications: A survey](#) (Unai Alegre, Juan Carlos Augusto, Tony Clark)
6. [SIT: Sampling-based interactive testing for self-adaptive apps](#) (Yi Qin, Chang Xu, Ping Yu, Jian Lu)
7. [Twenty-eight years of component-based software engineering](#) (Tassio Vale, Ivica Crnkovic, Eduardo Santana de Almeida, Paulo Anselmo da Mota Silveira Neto, Yguaratã Cerqueira Cavalcanti, Silvio Romero de Lemos Meira)
8. [10 years of software architecture knowledge management: Practice and future](#) (Rafael Capilla, Anton Jansen, Antony Tang, Paris Avgeriou, Muhammad Ali Babar)
9. [A systematic mapping study of mobile application testing techniques](#) (Samer Zein, Norsaremah Salleh, John Grundy)
10. [Enabling public auditing for shared data in cloud storage supporting identity privacy and traceability](#) (Guangyang Yang, Jia Yu, Wenting Shen, Qianqian Su, Zhangjie Fu, Rong Hao)

Information and Software Technology 2016

1. [Identification and management of technical debt: A systematic mapping study](#) (Nicoli S.R. Alves, Thiago S. Mendes, Manoel G. de Mendonça, Rodrigo O. Spínola, Forrest Shull, Carolyn Seaman)
2. [Reviewer recommendation for pull-requests in GitHub: What can we learn from code review and bug assignment?](#) (Yue Yu, Huaimin Wang, Gang Yin, Tao Wang)
3. [Tuning for software analytics: Is it really necessary?](#) (Wei Fu, Tim Menzies, Xipeng Shen)
4. [Challenges and best practices in industry-academia collaborations in software engineering: A systematic literature review](#) (Vahid Garousi, Kai Petersen, Baris Ozkan)
5. [When and what to automate in software testing? A multi-vocal literature review](#) (Vahid Garousi, Mika V. Mäntylä)
6. [Challenges of project management in global software development: A client-vendor analysis](#) (Mahmood Niazi, Sajjad Mahmood, Mohammad Alshayeb, Mohammed Rehan Riaz, Kanaan Faisal, Narciso Cerpa, Siffat Ullah Khan, Ita Richardson)

7. [The challenges that challenge: Engaging with agile practitioners' concerns](#) (Peggy Gregory, Leonor Barroca, Helen Sharp, Advait Deshpande, Katie Taylor)
8. [A systematic literature review of literature reviews in software testing](#) (Vahid Garousi, Mika V. Mäntylä)
9. [Effective detection of android malware based on the usage of data flow APIs and machine learning](#) (Songyang Wu, Pan Wang, Xun Li, Yong Zhang)
10. [Artefacts and agile method tailoring in large-scale offshore software development programmes](#) (Julian M. Bass)

Empirical Software Engineering 2016

1. [Automatic repair of real bugs in java: a large-scale experiment on the defects4j dataset](#) (Matias Martinez, Thomas Durieux, Romain Sommerard, Jifeng Xuan, Martin Monperus)
2. [Naming the pain in requirements engineering](#) (D. Méndez Fernández, S. Wagner, M. Kalinowski, M. Felderer, P. Mafra, A. Vetrò, T. Conte, M.-T. Christiansson, D. Greer, C. Lassenius, T. Männistö, M. Nayabi, M. Oivo, B. Penzenstadler, D. Pfahl, R. Prikladnicki, G. Ruhe, A. Schekelmann, S. Sen, R. Spinola, A. Tuzcu, J. L. de la Vara, R. Wieringa)
3. [Why and how developers fork what from whom in GitHub](#) (Jing Jiang, David Lo, Jiahuan He, Xin Xia, Pavneet Singh Kochhar, Li Zhang)
4. [Characterizing logging practices in Java-based open source software projects – a replication study in Apache Software Foundation](#) (Boyuan Chen, Zhen Ming (Jack) Jiang)
5. [“Failures” to be celebrated: an analysis of major pivots of software startups](#) (Sohaib Shahid Bajwa, Xiaofeng Wang, Anh Nguyen Duc, Pekka Abrahamsson)
6. [Learning to rank code examples for code search engines](#) (Haoran Niu, Iman Keivanloo, Ying Zou)
7. [How programmers read regular code: a controlled experiment using eye tracking](#) (Ahmad Jbara, Dror G. Feitelson)
8. [Negative results for software effort estimation](#) (Tim Menzies, Ye Yang, George Mathew, Barry Boehm, Jairus Hihn)
9. [A large-scale study of architectural evolution in open-source software systems](#) (Pooyan Behnamghader, Duc Minh Le, Joshua Garcia, Daniel Link, Arman Shahbazian, Nenad Medvidovic)
10. [Which log level should developers choose for a new logging statement?](#) (Heng Li, Weiyi Shang, Ahmed E. Hassan)

Proceedings of the 2016 24th ACM SIGSOFT International Symposium on Foundations of Software Engineering

1. [Deep API learning](#) (Xiaodong Gu, Hongyu Zhang, Dongmei Zhang, Sunghun Kim)
2. [Why we refactor? confessions of GitHub contributors](#) (Danilo Silva, Nikolaos Tsantalis, Marco Tulio Valente)
3. [Effort-aware just-in-time defect prediction: simple unsupervised models could be better than supervised models](#) (Yibiao Yang, Yuming Zhou, Jinping Liu, Yangyang Zhao, Hongmin Lu, Lei Xu, Baowen Xu, Hareton Leung)
4. [BinGo: cross-architecture cross-OS binary search](#) (Mahinthan Chandramohan, Yinxing Xue, Zhengzi Xu, Yang Liu, Chia Yuan Cho, Hee Beng Kuan Tan)
5. [How to break an API: cost negotiation and community values in three software ecosystems](#) (Christopher Bogart, Christian Kästner, James Herbsleb, Ferdian Thung)
6. [API code recommendation using statistical learning from fine-grained changes](#) (Anh Tuan Nguyen, Michael Hilton, Mihai Codoban, Hoan Anh Nguyen, Lily Mast, Eli Rademacher, Tien N. Nguyen, Danny Dig)
7. [Anti-patterns in search-based program repair](#) (Shin Hwei Tan, Hiroaki Yoshida, Mukul R. Prasad, Abhik Roychoudhury)
8. [Disrupting developer productivity one bot at a time](#) (Margaret-Anne Storey, Alexey Zagalsky)
9. [What would users change in my app? summarizing app reviews for recommending software changes](#) (Andrea Di Sorbo, Sebastiano Panichella, Carol V. Alexandru, Junji Shimagaki, Corrado A. Visaggio, Gerardo Canfora, Harald C. Gall)
10. [An extensive study of static regression test selection in modern software evolution](#) (Owolabi Legunsen, Farah Hariri, August Shi, Yafeng Lu, Lingming Zhang, Darko Marinov)

Proceedings of the 31st IEEE/ACM International Conference on Automated Software Engineering 2016

1. [Deep learning code fragments for code clone detection](#) (Martin White, Michele Tufano, Christopher Vendome, Denys Poshyvanyk)
2. [Usage, costs, and benefits of continuous integration in open-source projects](#) (Michael Hilton, Timothy Tunnell, Kai Huang, Darko Marinov, Danny Dig)
3. [What developers want and need from program analysis: an empirical study](#) (Maria Christakis, Christian Bird)
4. [Testing advanced driver assistance systems using multi-objective search and neural networks](#) (Raja Ben Abdesslem, Shiva Nejati, Lionel C. Briand, Thomas Stifter)

5. [Taming Android fragmentation: characterizing and detecting compatibility issues for Android apps](#) (Lili Wei, Yepang Liu, Shing-Chi Cheung)
6. [Locus: locating bugs from software changes](#) (Ming Wen, Rongxin Wu, Shing-Chi Cheung)
7. [Automated model-based Android GUI testing using multi-level GUI comparison criteria](#) (Young-Min Baek, Doo-Hwan Bae)
8. [Predicting semantically linkable knowledge in developer online forums via convolutional neural network](#) (Bowen Xu, Deheng Ye, Zhenchang Xing, Xin Xia, Guibin Chen, Shanping Li)
9. [An empirical investigation into the nature of test smells](#) (Michele Tufano, Fabio Palomba, Gabriele Bavota, Massimiliano Di Penta, Rocco Oliveto, Andrea De Lucia, Denys Poshyvanyk)
10. [Bugram: bug detection with n-gram language models](#) (Song Wang, Devin Chollak, Dana Movshovitz-Attias, Lin Tan)

ACM Transactions on Software Engineering and Methodology 2016

1. [Multi-Criteria Code Refactoring Using Search-Based Software Engineering](#) (Ali Ouni, Marouane Kessentini, Houari Sahraoui, Katsuro Inoue, Kalyanmoy Deb)
2. [Using Cohesion and Coupling for Software Remodularization](#) (Ivan Candela, Gabriele Bavota, Barbara Russo, Rocco Oliveto)
3. [Inflow and Retention in OSS Communities with Commercial Involvement](#) (Minghui Zhou, Audris Mockus, Xiujuan Ma, Lu Zhang, Hong Mei)
4. [Impact-Driven Process Model Repair](#) (Artem Polyvyanyy, Wil M. P. Van Der Aalst, Arthur H. M. Ter Hofstede, Moe T. Wynn)
5. [Mining Privacy Goals from Privacy Policies Using Hybridized Task Recomposition](#) (Jaspreet Bhatia, Travis D. Breaux, Florian Schaub)
6. [The Effect of Program and Model Structure on the Effectiveness of MC/DC Test Adequacy Coverage](#) (Gregory Gay, Ajitha Rajan, Matt Staats, Michael Whalen, Mats P. E. Heimdahl)
7. [Multi-Step Learning and Adaptive Search for Learning Complex Model Transformations from Examples](#) (Islem Baki, Houari Sahraoui)
8. [DiaPro](#) (Haipeng Cai, Raul Santelices, Douglas Thain)
9. [Learning Weighted Assumptions for Compositional Verification of Markov Decision Processes](#) (Fei He, Xiaowei Gao, Miaofei Wang, Bow-Yaw Wang, Lijun Zhang)
10. [Stochastic Performance Analysis of Global Software Development Teams](#) (Ricardo M. Czekster, Paulo Fernandes, Lucelene Lopes, Afonso Sales, Alan R. Santos, Thais Weber)

2017 IEEE/ACM 39th International Conference on Software Engineering

1. [Evaluating and Improving Fault Localization](#) (Spencer Pearson, Jose Campos, Rene Just, Gordon Fraser, Rui Abreu, Michael D. Ernst, Deric Pang, Benjamin Keller)
2. [Precise Condition Synthesis for Program Repair](#) (Yingfei Xiong, Jie Wang, Runfa Yan, Jiachen Zhang, Shi Han, Gang Huang, Lu Zhang)
3. [Semantically Enhanced Software Traceability Using Deep Learning Techniques](#) (Jin Guo, Jinghui Cheng, Jane Cleland-Huang)
4. [Learning Syntactic Program Transformations from Examples](#) (Reudismam Rolim, Gustavo Soares, Loris D'Antoni, Oleksandr Polozov, Sumit Gulwani, Rohit Gheyi, Ryo Suzuki, Bjorn Hartmann)
5. [Exploring API Embedding for API Usages and Applications](#) (Trong Duc Nguyen, Anh Tuan Nguyen, Hung Dang Phan, Tien N. Nguyen)
6. [LibD: Scalable and Precise Third-Party Library Detection in Android Markets](#) (Menghao Li, Wei Wang, Pei Wang, Shuai Wang, Dinghao Wu, Jian Liu, Rui Xue, Wei Huo)
7. [Recommending and Localizing Change Requests for Mobile Apps Based on User Reviews](#) (Fabio Palomba, Pasquale Salza, Adelina Ciurumelea, Sebastiano Panichella, Harald Gall, Filomena Ferrucci, Andrea De Lucia)
8. [An Empirical Study on Mutation, Statement and Branch Coverage Fault Revelation That Avoids the Unreliable Clean Program Assumption](#) (Thierry Titchou Chekam, Mike Papadakis, Yves Le Traon, Mark Harman)
9. [SPAIN: Security Patch Analysis for Binaries towards Understanding the Pain and Pills](#) (Zhengzi Xu, Bihuan Chen, Mahinthan Chandramohan, Yang Liu, Fu Song)
10. [Decoding the Representation of Code in the Brain: An fMRI Study of Code Review and Expertise](#) (Benjamin Floyd, Tyler Santander, Westley Weimer)

IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering 2017

1. [An Empirical Comparison of Model Validation Techniques for Defect Prediction Models](#) (Chakrit Tantithamthavorn, Shane McIntosh, Ahmed E. Hassan, Kenichi Matsumoto)
2. [A Survey of App Store Analysis for Software Engineering](#) (William Martin, Federica Sarro, Yue Jia, Yuanyuan Zhang, Mark Harman)
3. [Nopol: Automatic Repair of Conditional Statement Bugs in Java Programs](#) (Jifeng Xuan, Matias Martinez, Favio DeMarco, Maxime Clement, Sebastian Lamelas Marcote, Thomas Durieux, Daniel Le Berre, Martin Monperrus)
4. [When and Why Your Code Starts to Smell Bad \(and Whether the Smells Go Away\)](#) (Michele Tufano, Fabio Palomba, Gabriele Bavota, Rocco Oliveto, Massimiliano Di Penta, Andrea De Lucia, Denys Poshyvanyk)

5. [How Social and Communication Channels Shape and Challenge a Participatory Culture in Software Development](#) (Margaret-Anne Storey, Alexey Zagalsky, Fernando Figueira Filho, Leif Singer, Daniel M. German)
6. [Using Natural Language Processing to Automatically Detect Self-Admitted Technical Debt](#) (Everton da Silva Maldonado, Emad Shihab, Nikolaos Tsantalis)
7. [A Framework for Evaluating the Results of the SZZ Approach for Identifying Bug-Introducing Changes](#) (Daniel Alencar da Costa, Shane McIntosh, Weiyi Shang, Uira Kulesza, Roberta Coelho, Ahmed E. Hassan)
8. [An Improved SDA Based Defect Prediction Framework for Both Within-Project and Cross-Project Class-Imbalance Problems](#) (Xiao-Yuan Jing, Fei Wu, Xiwei Dong, Baowen Xu)
9. [Improving Automated Bug Triaging with Specialized Topic Model](#) (Xin Xia, David Lo, Ying Ding, Jafar M. Al-Kofahi, Tien N. Nguyen, Xinyu Wang)
10. [The Work Life of Developers: Activities, Switches and Perceived Productivity](#) (Andre N. Meyer, Laura E. Barton, Gail C. Murphy, Thomas Zimmermann, Thomas Fritz)

Journal of Systems and Software 2017

1. [Continuous software engineering: A roadmap and agenda](#) (Brian Fitzgerald, Klaas-Jan Stol)
2. [A survey of the use of crowdsourcing in software engineering](#) (Ke Mao, Licia Capra, Mark Harman, Yue Jia)
3. [A systematic literature review: Opinion mining studies from mobile app store user reviews](#) (Necmiye Genc-Nayebi, Alain Abran)
4. [An improved genetic algorithm for task scheduling in the cloud environments using the priority queues: Formal verification, simulation, and statistical testing](#) (Bahman Keshanchi, Alireza Souri, Nima Jafari Navimipour)
5. [Continuous deployment of software intensive products and services: A systematic mapping study](#) (Pilar Rodríguez, Alireza Haghghatkah, Lucy Ellen Lwakatere, Susanna Teppola, Tanja Suomalainen, Juho Eskeli, Teemu Karvonen, Pasi Kuvaja, June M. Verner, Markku Oivo)
6. [Understanding cloud-native applications after 10 years of cloud computing - A systematic mapping study](#) (Nane Kratzke, Peter-Christian Quint)
7. [Rapid quality assurance with Requirements Smells](#) (Henning Femmer, Daniel Méndez Fernández, Stefan Wagner, Sebastian Eder)
8. [The RIGHT model for Continuous Experimentation](#) (Fabian Fagerholm, Alejandro Sanchez Guinea, Hanna Mäenpää, Jürgen Münch)

9. [Performance evaluation of cloud-based log file analysis with Apache Hadoop and Apache Spark](#) (Ilias Mavridis, Helen Karatza)
10. [Source code metrics: A systematic mapping study](#) (Alberto S. Nuñez-Varela, Héctor G. Pérez-Gonzalez, Francisco E. Martínez-Perez, Carlos Soubervielle-Montalvo)

Information and Software Technology 2017

1. [Static analysis of android apps: A systematic literature review](#) (Li Li, Tegawendé F. Bis-syandé, Mike Papadakis, Siegfried Rasthofer, Alexandre Bartel, Damien Octeau, Jacques Klein, Le Traon)
2. [TLEL: A two-layer ensemble learning approach for just-in-time defect prediction](#) (Xinli Yang, David Lo, Xin Xia, Jianling Sun)
3. [Systematic literature reviews in agile software development: A tertiary study](#) (Rashina Hoda, Norsaremah Salleh, John Grundy, Hui Mien Tee)
4. [Systematic literature review and empirical investigation of barriers to process improvement in global software development: Client–vendor perspective](#) (Arif Ali Khan, Jacky Keung, Mahmood Niazi, Shahid Hussain, Awais Ahmad)
5. [Taxonomies in software engineering: A Systematic mapping study and a revised taxonomy development method](#) (Muhammad Usman, Ricardo Britto, Jürgen Börstler, Emilia Mendes)
6. [Problems, causes and solutions when adopting continuous delivery—A systematic literature review](#) (Eero Laukkanen, Juha Itkonen, Casper Lassenius)
7. [On code reuse from StackOverflow: An exploratory study on Android apps](#) (Rabe Abdalkareem, Emad Shihab, Juergen Rilling)
8. [Software teams and their knowledge networks in large-scale software development](#) (Darja Šmite, Nils Brede Moe, Aivars Šāblis, Claes Wohlin)
9. [Analyzing the concept of technical debt in the context of agile software development: A systematic literature review](#) (Woubshet Nema Behutiye, Pilar Rodríguez, Markku Oivo, Ayşe Tosun)
10. [Software test maturity assessment and test process improvement: A multivocal literature review](#) (Vahid Garousi, Michael Felderer, Tuna Hacaloğlu)

Empirical Software Engineering 2017

1. [Curating GitHub for engineered software projects](#) (Nuthan Munaiah, Steven Kroh, Craig Cabrey, Meiyappan Nagappan)
2. [Do developers update their library dependencies?](#) (Raula Gaikovina Kula, Daniel M. German, Ali Ouni, Takashi Ishio, Katsuro Inoue)

3. [On the diffuseness and the impact on maintainability of code smells: a large scale empirical investigation](#) (Fabio Palomba, Gabriele Bavota, Massimiliano Di Penta, Fausto Fasano, Rocco Oliveto, Andrea De Lucia)
4. [Sentiment Polarity Detection for Software Development](#) (Fabio Calefato, Filippo Lanubile, Federico Maiorano, Nicole Novielli)
5. [Empirical software engineering experts on the use of students and professionals in experiments](#) (Davide Falessi, Natalia Juristo, Claes Wohlin, Burak Turhan, Jürgen Münch, Andreas Jedlitschka, Markku Oivo)
6. [Exploring software development at the very large-scale: a revelatory case study and research agenda for agile method adaptation](#) (Torgeir Dingsøy, Nils Brede Moe, Tor Erlend Fægri, Eva Amdahl Seim)
7. [Privacy by designers: software developers' privacy mindset](#) (Irit Hadar, Tomer Hasson, Oshrat Ayalon, Eran Toch, Michael Birnhack, Sofia Sherman, Arod Balissa)
8. [On negative results when using sentiment analysis tools for software engineering research](#) (Robbert Jongeling, Proshanta Sarkar, Subhajit Datta, Alexander Serebrenik)
9. [What do developers search for on the web?](#) (Xin Xia, Lingfeng Bao, David Lo, Pavneet Singh Kochhar, Ahmed E. Hassan, Zhenchang Xing)
10. [Identifying self-admitted technical debt in open source projects using text mining](#) (Qiao Huang, Emad Shihab, Xin Xia, David Lo, Shanping Li)

Proceedings of the 2017 11th Joint Meeting on Foundations of Software Engineering

1. [Fairness testing: testing software for discrimination](#) (Sainyam Galhotra, Yuriy Brun, Alexandra Meliou)
2. [Are deep neural networks the best choice for modeling source code?](#) (Vincent J. Hellendoorn, Premkumar Devanbu)
3. [Guided, stochastic model-based GUI testing of Android apps](#) (Ting Su, Guozhu Meng, Yuting Chen, Ke Wu, Weiming Yang, Yao Yao, Geguang Pu, Yang Liu, Zhendong Su)
4. [Steelix: program-state based binary fuzzing](#) (Yuekang Li, Bihuan Chen, Mahinthan Chandramohan, Shang-Wei Lin, Yang Liu, Alwen Tiu)
5. [S3: syntax- and semantic-guided repair synthesis via programming by examples](#) (Xuan-Bach D. Le, Duc-Hiep Chu, David Lo, Claire Le Goues, Willem Visser)
6. [Easy over hard: a case study on deep learning](#) (Wei Fu, Tim Menzies)
7. [Automatic inference of code transforms for patch generation](#) (Fan Long, Peter Amidon, Martin Rinard)
8. [Trade-offs in continuous integration: assurance, security, and flexibility](#) (Michael Hilton, Nicholas Nelson, Timothy Tunnell, Darko Marinov, Danny Dig)

9. [Serverless computing: economic and architectural impact](#) (Gojko Adzic, Robert Chatley)
10. [Automated identification of security issues from commit messages and bug reports](#) (Yaqin Zhou, Asankhaya Sharma)

2017 32nd IEEE/ACM International Conference on Automated Software Engineering

1. [Learn&Fuzz: Machine learning for input fuzzing](#) (Patrice Godefroid, Hila Peleg, Rishabh Singh)
2. [Automatically generating commit messages from diffs using neural machine translation](#) (Siyuan Jiang, Ameer Armaly, Collin McMillan)
3. [Elixir: Effective object-oriented program repair](#) (Ripon K. Saha, Yingjun Lyu, Hiroaki Yoshida, Mukul R. Prasad)
4. [Leveraging syntax-related code for automated program repair](#) (Qi Xin, Steven P. Reiss)
5. [The impact of continuous integration on other software development practices: A large-scale empirical study](#) (Yangyang Zhao, Alexander Serebrenik, Yuming Zhou, Vladimir Filkov, Bogdan Vasilescu)
6. [Contract-based program repair without the contracts](#) (Liushan Chen, Yu Pei, Carlo A. Furia)
7. [Can automated pull requests encourage software developers to upgrade out-of-date dependencies?](#) (Samim Mirhosseini, Chris Parnin)
8. [SentiCR: A customized sentiment analysis tool for code review interactions](#) (Toufique Ahmed, Amiangshu Bosu, Anindya Iqbal, Shahram Rahimi)
9. [AnswerBot: Automated generation of answer summary to developers' technical questions](#) (Bowen Xu, Zhenchang Xing, Xin Xia, David Lo)
10. [Transfer learning for performance modeling of configurable systems: An exploratory analysis](#) (Pooyan Jamshidi, Norbert Siegmund, Miguel Velez, Christian Kastner, Akshay Patel, Yuvraj Agarwal)

ACM Transactions on Software Engineering and Methodology 2017

1. [Lightweight, Obfuscation-Resilient Detection and Family Identification of Android Malware](#) (Joshua Garcia, Mahmoud Hammad, Sam Malek)
2. [Variability Bugs in Highly Configurable Systems](#) (Iago Abal, Jean Melo, Ștefan Stănculescu, Claus Brabrand, Márcio Ribeiro, Andrzej Wařowski)
3. [Configuring Software Product Lines by Combining Many-Objective Optimization and SAT Solvers](#) (Yi Xiang, Yuren Zhou, Zibin Zheng, Miqing Li)

4. [Human Competitiveness of Genetic Programming in Spectrum-Based Fault Localisation](#) (Shin Yoo, Xiaoyuan Xie, Fei-Ching Kuo, Tsong Yueh Chen, Mark Harman)
5. [Predicting Query Quality for Applications of Text Retrieval to Software Engineering Tasks](#) (Chris Mills, Gabriele Bavota, Sonia Haiduc, Rocco Oliveto, Andrian Marcus, Andrea De Lucia)
6. [Generating API Call Rules from Version History and Stack Overflow Posts](#) (Shams Azad, Peter C. Rigby, Latifa Guerrouj)
7. [Fixing Faults in C and Java Source Code](#) (Giuseppe Scanniello, Michele Risi, Porfirio Tramontana, Simone Romano)
8. [Detecting the Behavior of Design Patterns through Model Checking and Dynamic Analysis](#) (Andrea De Lucia, Vincenzo Deufemia, Carmine Gravino, Michele Risi)
9. [Parallel Algorithms for Generating Distinguishing Sequences for Observable Non-deterministic FSMs](#) (Robert M. Hierons, Uraz Cengiz Türker)
10. [Augmenting Field Data for Testing Systems Subject to Incremental Requirements Changes](#) (Daniel Di Nardo, Fabrizio Pastore, Lionel Briand)

Proceedings of the 40th International Conference on Software Engineering 2018

1. [DeepTest](#) (Yuchi Tian, Kexin Pei, Suman Jana, Baishakhi Ray)
2. [Deep code search](#) (Xiaodong Gu, Hongyu Zhang, Sunghun Kim)
3. [Automatic software repair](#) (Luca Gazzola, Daniela Micucci, Leonardo Mariani)
4. [Context-aware patch generation for better automated program repair](#) (Ming Wen, Junjie Chen, Rongxin Wu, Dan Hao, Shing-Chi Cheung)
5. [Accurate and efficient refactoring detection in commit history](#) (Nikolaos Tsantalis, Matin Mansouri, Laleh M. Eshkevari, Davood Mazinanian, Danny Dig)
6. [Measuring program comprehension](#) (Xin Xia, Lingfeng Bao, David Lo, Zhenchang Xing, Ahmed E. Hassan, Shanping Li)
7. [MAHAKIL](#) (Kwabena E. Bennin, Jacky Keung, Passakorn Phannachitta, Akito Monden, Solomon Mensah)
8. [Testing vision-based control systems using learnable evolutionary algorithms](#) (Raja Ben Abdessalem, Shiva Nejati, Lionel C. Briand, Thomas Stifter)
9. [From UI design image to GUI skeleton](#) (Chunyang Chen, Ting Su, Guozhu Meng, Zhenchang Xing, Yang Liu)
10. [Sentiment analysis for software engineering](#) (Bin Lin, Fiorella Zampetti, Gabriele Bavota, Massimiliano Di Penta, Michele Lanza, Rocco Oliveto)

IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering 2018

1. [Automated Test Case Generation as a Many-Objective Optimisation Problem with Dynamic Selection of the Targets](#) (Annibale Panichella, Fitsum Meshesha Kifetew, Paolo Tonella)
2. [Are Fix-Inducing Changes a Moving Target? A Longitudinal Case Study of Just-In-Time Defect Prediction](#) (Shane McIntosh, Yasutaka Kamei)
3. [Engineering Trustworthy Self-Adaptive Software with Dynamic Assurance Cases](#) (Radu Calinescu, Danny Weyns, Simos Gerasimou, Muhammad Usman Iftikhar, Ibrahim Habli, Tim Kelly)
4. [Metamorphic Testing of RESTful Web APIs](#) (Sergio Segura, Jose A. Parejo, Javier Troya, Antonio Ruiz-Cortes)
5. [A Developer Centered Bug Prediction Model](#) (Dario Di Nucci, Fabio Palomba, Giuseppe De Rosa, Gabriele Bavota, Rocco Oliveto, Andrea De Lucia)
6. [Coordination Challenges in Large-Scale Software Development: A Case Study of Planning Misalignment in Hybrid Settings](#) (Saskia Bick, Kai Spohrer, Rashina Hoda, Alexander Scheerer, Armin Heinzl)
7. [Detecting Trivial Mutant Equivalences via Compiler Optimisations](#) (Marinos Kintis, Mike Papadakis, Yue Jia, Nicos Malevris, Yves Le Traon, Mark Harman)
8. [Control-Theoretical Software Adaptation: A Systematic Literature Review](#) (Stepan Shevtsov, Mihaly Berekmeri, Danny Weyns, Martina Maggio)
9. [Empirical Evaluation of the Impact of Object-Oriented Code Refactoring on Quality Attributes: A Systematic Literature Review](#) (Jehad Al Dallal, Anas Abdin)
10. [Complete and Interpretable Conformance Checking of Business Processes](#) (Luciano Garcia-Banuelos, Nick R.T.P. van Beest, Marlon Dumas, Marcello La Rosa, Willem Mertens)

Journal of Systems and Software 2018

1. [The pains and gains of microservices: A Systematic grey literature review](#) (Jacopo Soldani, Damian Andrew Tamburri, Willem-Jan Van Den Heuvel)
2. [What's in a GitHub Star? Understanding Repository Starring Practices in a Social Coding Platform](#) (Hudson Borges, Marco Tulio Valente)
3. [A survey on software smells](#) (Tushar Sharma, Diomidis Spinellis)
4. [What happens when software developers are \(un\)happy](#) (Daniel Graziotin, Fabian Fagerholm, Xiaofeng Wang, Pekka Abrahamsson)
5. [An effective approach for software project effort and duration estimation with machine learning algorithms](#) (Przemyslaw Pospieszny, Beata Czarnacka-Chrobot, Andrzej Kobylinski)

6. [Software sustainability: Research and practice from a software architecture viewpoint](#) (Colin C. Venters, Rafael Capilla, Stefanie Betz, Birgit Penzenstadler, Tom Crick, Steve Crouch, Elisa Yumi Nakagawa, Christoph Becker, Carlos Carrillo)
7. [Smells in software test code: A survey of knowledge in industry and academia](#) (Vahid Garousi, Barış Küçük)
8. [Monitoring self-adaptive applications within edge computing frameworks: A state-of-the-art review](#) (Salman Taherizadeh, Andrew C. Jones, Ian Taylor, Zhiming Zhao, Vlado Stankovski)
9. [Adaptive generation of challenging scenarios for testing and evaluation of autonomous vehicles](#) (Galen E. Mullins, Paul G. Stankiewicz, R. Chad Hawthorne, Satyandra K. Gupta)
10. [Software startup engineering: A systematic mapping study](#) (Vebjørn Berg, Jørgen Birke-land, Anh Nguyen-Duc, Ilias O. Pappas, Letizia Jaccheri)

Information and Software Technology 2018

1. [How to design gamification? A method for engineering gamified software](#) (Benedikt Morschheuser, Lobna Hassan, Karl Werder, Juho Hamari)
2. [What is wrong with topic modeling? And how to fix it using search-based software engineering](#) (Amritanshu Agrawal, Wei Fu, Tim Menzies)
3. [Test case prioritization approaches in regression testing: A systematic literature review](#) (Muhammad Khatibsyarbini, Mohd Adham Isa, Dayang N.A. Jawawi, Rooster Tumeng)
4. [A tertiary study on technical debt: Types, management strategies, research trends, and base information for practitioners](#) (Nicolli Rios, Manoel Gomes de Mendonça Neto, Rodrigo Oliveira Spínola)
5. [Software defect prediction using stacked denoising autoencoders and two-stage ensemble learning](#) (Haonan Tong, Bin Liu, Shihai Wang)
6. [MULTI: Multi-objective effort-aware just-in-time software defect prediction](#) (Xiang Chen, Yingquan Zhao, Qiuping Wang, Zhidan Yuan)
7. [How to ask for technical help? Evidence-based guidelines for writing questions on Stack Overflow](#) (Fabio Calefato, Filippo Lanubile, Nicole Novielli)
8. [Systematic literature review on agile practices in global software development](#) (Raoul Vallon, Bernardo José da Silva Estácio, Rafael Prikladnicki, Thomas Grechenig)
9. [A systematic mapping study on game-related methods for software engineering education](#) (Mauricio R. de A. Souza, Lucas Veado, Renata Teles Moreira, Eduardo Figueiredo, Heitor Costa)
10. [A systematic review of requirements change management](#) (Shalinka Jayatilleke, Richard Lai)

Empirical Software Engineering 2018

1. [An empirical comparison of dependency network evolution in seven software packaging ecosystems](#) (Alexandre Decan, Tom Mens, Philippe Grosjean)
2. [Large-scale agile transformation at Ericsson: a case study](#) (Maria Paasivaara, Benjamin Behm, Casper Lassenius, Minna Hallikainen)
3. [Categorizing the Content of GitHub README Files](#) (Gede Artha Azriadi Prana, Christoph Treude, Ferdian Thung, Thushari Atapattu, David Lo)
4. [Shorter identifier names take longer to comprehend](#) (Johannes C. Hofmeister, Janet Siegmund, Daniel V. Holt)
5. [How do developers utilize source code from stack overflow?](#) (Yuhao Wu, Shaowei Wang, Cor-Paul Bezemer, Katsuro Inoue)
6. [Revisiting supervised and unsupervised models for effort-aware just-in-time defect prediction](#) (Qiao Huang, Xin Xia, David Lo)
7. [Overfitting in semantics-based automated program repair](#) (Xuan Bach D. Le, Ferdian Thung, David Lo, Claire Le Goues)
8. [An empirical study of game reviews on the Steam platform](#) (Dayi Lin, Cor-Paul Bezemer, Ying Zou, Ahmed E. Hassan)
9. [Test them all, is it worth it? Assessing configuration sampling on the JHipster Web development stack](#) (Axel Halin, Alexandre Nuttinck, Mathieu Acher, Xavier Devroey, Gilles Perrouin, Benoit Baudry)
10. [Software engineering in start-up companies: An analysis of 88 experience reports](#) (Eriks Klotins, Michael Unterkalmsteiner, Tony Gorschek)

Proceedings of the 2018 26th ACM Joint Meeting on European Software Engineering Conference and Symposium on the Foundations of Software Engineering

1. [PyDriller: Python framework for mining software repositories](#) (Davide Spadini, Maurício Aniche, Alberto Bacchelli)
2. [DLFuzz: differential fuzzing testing of deep learning systems](#) (Jianmin Guo, Yu Jiang, Yue Zhao, Quan Chen, Jianguang Sun)
3. [DeepSim: deep learning code functional similarity](#) (Gang Zhao, Jeff Huang)
4. [Deep learning type inference](#) (Vincent J. Hellendoorn, Christian Bird, Earl T. Barr, Miltiadis Allamanis)
5. [Does ACM's code of ethics change ethical decision making in software development?](#) (Andrew McNamara, Justin Smith, Emerson Murphy-Hill)

6. [MODE: automated neural network model debugging via state differential analysis and input selection](#) (Shiqing Ma, Yingqi Liu, Wen-Chuan Lee, Xiangyu Zhang, Ananth Grama)
7. [Identifying impactful service system problems via log analysis](#) (Shilin He, Qingwei Lin, Jian-Guang Lou, Hongyu Zhang, Michael R. Lyu, Dongmei Zhang)
8. [Oreo: detection of clones in the twilight zone](#) (Vaibhav Saini, Farima Farmahinifarahani, Yadong Lu, Pierre Baldi, Cristina V. Lopes)
9. [Ecosystem-level determinants of sustained activity in open-source projects: a case study of the PyPI ecosystem](#) (Marat Valiev, Bogdan Vasilescu, James Herbsleb)
10. [Software fairness](#) (Yuriy Brun, Alexandra Meliou)

Proceedings of the 33rd ACM/IEEE International Conference on Automated Software Engineering 2018

1. [ContractFuzzer: fuzzing smart contracts for vulnerability detection](#) (Bo Jiang, Ye Liu, W. K. Chan)
2. [DeepGauge: multi-granularity testing criteria for deep learning systems](#) (Lei Ma, Felix Juefei-Xu, Fuyuan Zhang, Jiyuan Sun, Minhui Xue, Bo Li, Chunyang Chen, Ting Su, Li Li, Yang Liu, Jianjun Zhao, Yadong Wang)
3. [DeepRoad: GAN-based metamorphic testing and input validation framework for autonomous driving systems](#) (Mengshi Zhang, Yuqun Zhang, Lingming Zhang, Cong Liu, Sarfraz Khurshid)
4. [FairFuzz: a targeted mutation strategy for increasing greybox fuzz testing coverage](#) (Caroline Lemieux, Koushik Sen)
5. [Improving automatic source code summarization via deep reinforcement learning](#) (Yao Wan, Zhou Zhao, Min Yang, Guandong Xu, Haochao Ying, Jian Wu, Philip S. Yu)
6. [Concolic testing for deep neural networks](#) (Youcheng Sun, Min Wu, Wenjie Ruan, Xiaowei Huang, Marta Kwiatkowska, Daniel Kroening)
7. [Neural-machine-translation-based commit message generation: how far are we?](#) (Zhongxin Liu, Xin Xia, Ahmed E. Hassan, David Lo, Zhenchang Xing, Xinyu Wang)
8. [aDiff: cross-version binary code similarity detection with DNN](#) (Bingchang Liu, Wei Huo, Chao Zhang, Wenchao Li, Feng Li, Aihua Piao, Wei Zou)
9. [API method recommendation without worrying about the task-API knowledge gap](#) (Qiao Huang, Xin Xia, Zhenchang Xing, David Lo, Xinyu Wang)
10. [VulSeeker: a semantic learning based vulnerability seeker for cross-platform binary](#) (Jian Gao, Xin Yang, Ying Fu, Yu Jiang, Jianguang Sun)

ACM Transactions on Software Engineering and Methodology 2018

1. [The ABC of Software Engineering Research](#) (Klaas-Jan Stol, Brian Fitzgerald)
2. [How Far We Have Progressed in the Journey? An Examination of Cross-Project Defect Prediction](#) (Yuming Zhou, Yibiao Yang, Hongmin Lu, Lin Chen, Yanhui Li, Yangyang Zhao, Junyan Qian, Baowen Xu)
3. [Variability-Aware Static Analysis at Scale](#) (Alexander Von Rhein, JÖRG Liebig, Andreas Janker, Christian Kästner, Sven Apel)
4. [FEMOSAA](#) (Tao Chen, Ke Li, Rami Bahsoon, Xin Yao)
5. [Test-Equivalence Analysis for Automatic Patch Generation](#) (Sergey Mechtaev, Xiang Gao, Shin Hwei Tan, Abhik Roychoudhury)
6. [Linear Programming as a Baseline for Software Effort Estimation](#) (Federica Sarro, Alessio Petrozziello)
7. [An Empirical Study of Meta- and Hyper-Heuristic Search for Multi-Objective Release Planning](#) (Yuanyuan Zhang, Mark Harman, Gabriela Ochoa, Guenther Ruhe, Sjaak Brinkkemper)
8. [Spectrum-Based Fault Localization in Model Transformations](#) (Javier Troya, Sergio Segura, Jose Antonio Parejo, Antonio Ruiz-Cortés)
9. [The State of Empirical Evaluation in Static Feature Location](#) (Abdul Razzaq, Asanka Wasala, Chris Exton, Jim Buckley)
10. [STADS](#) (Marcel Böhme)

2019 IEEE/ACM 41st International Conference on Software Engineering

1. [A Novel Neural Source Code Representation Based on Abstract Syntax Tree](#) (Jian Zhang, Xu Wang, Hongyu Zhang, Hailong Sun, Kaixuan Wang, Xudong Liu)
2. [Guiding Deep Learning System Testing Using Surprise Adequacy](#) (Jinhan Kim, Robert Feldt, Shin Yoo)
3. [A Neural Model for Generating Natural Language Summaries of Program Subroutines](#) (Alexander LeClair, Siyuan Jiang, Collin McMillan)
4. [Superion: Grammar-Aware Greybox Fuzzing](#) (Junjie Wang, Bihuan Chen, Lei Wei, Yang Liu)
5. [On Learning Meaningful Code Changes Via Neural Machine Translation](#) (Michele Tufano, Jevgenija Pantiuchina, Cody Watson, Gabriele Bavota, Denys Poshyvanyk)
6. [Adversarial Sample Detection for Deep Neural Network through Model Mutation Testing](#) (Jingyi Wang, Guoliang Dong, Jun Sun, Xinyu Wang, Peixin Zhang)

7. [RESTler: Stateful REST API Fuzzing](#) (Vaggelis Atlidakis, Patrice Godefroid, Marina Polishchuk)
8. [CRADLE: Cross-Backend Validation to Detect and Localize Bugs in Deep Learning Libraries](#) (Hung Viet Pham, Thibaud Lutellier, Weizhen Qi, Lin Tan)
9. [Software Documentation Issues Unveiled](#) (Emad Aghajani, Csaba Nagy, Olga Lucero Vega-Marquez, Mario Linares-Vasquez, Laura Moreno, Gabriele Bavota, Michele Lanza)
10. [The Seven Sins: Security Smells in Infrastructure as Code Scripts](#) (Akond Rahman, Chris Parnin, Laurie Williams)

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1. [The Impact of Automated Parameter Optimization on Defect Prediction Models](#) (Chakkrit Tantithamthavorn, Shane McIntosh, Ahmed E. Hassan, Kenichi Matsumoto)
2. [A Systematic Literature Review and Meta-Analysis on Cross Project Defect Prediction](#) (Seyedrebar Hosseini, Burak Turhan, Dimuthu Gunarathna)
3. [A Comprehensive Investigation of the Role of Imbalanced Learning for Software Defect Prediction](#) (Qinbao Song, Yuchen Guo, Martin Shepperd)
4. [Predictive Mutation Testing](#) (Jie Zhang, Lingming Zhang, Mark Harman, Dan Hao, Yue Jia, Lu Zhang)
5. [A Deep Learning Model for Estimating Story Points](#) (Morakot Choetkiertikul, Hoa Khanh Dam, Truyen Tran, Trang Pham, Aditya Ghose, Tim Menzies)
6. [Correction of “A Comparative Study to Benchmark Cross-Project Defect Prediction Approaches”](#) (Steffen Herbold, Alexander Trautsch, Jens Grabowski)
7. [A Systematic Evaluation of Static API-Misuse Detectors](#) (Sven Amann, Hoan Anh Nguyen, Sarah Nadi, Tien N. Nguyen, Mira Mezini)
8. [Toward a Smell-Aware Bug Prediction Model](#) (Fabio Palomba, Marco Zanoni, Francesca Arcelli Fontana, Andrea De Lucia, Rocco Oliveto)
9. [Developer Testing in the IDE: Patterns, Beliefs, and Behavior](#) (Moritz Beller, Georgios Gousios, Annibale Panichella, Sebastian Proksch, Sven Amann, Andy Zaidman)
10. [Listening to the Crowd for the Release Planning of Mobile Apps](#) (Simone Scalabrino, Gabriele Bavota, Barbara Russo, Massimiliano Di Penta, Rocco Oliveto)

Journal of Systems and Software 2019

1. [FogBus: A Blockchain-based Lightweight Framework for Edge and Fog Computing](#) (Shreshth Tuli, Redowan Mahmud, Shikhar Tuli, Rajkumar Buyya)
2. [End-user development, end-user programming and end-user software engineering: A systematic mapping study](#) (Barbara Rita Barricelli, Fabio Cassano, Daniela Fogli, Antonio Piccinno)

3. [Architecting with microservices: A systematic mapping study](#) (Paolo Di Francesco, Patricia Lago, Ivano Malavolta)
4. [State of the art of cyber-physical systems security: An automatic control perspective](#) (Yuriy Zacchia Lun, Alessandro D’Innocenzo, Francesco Smarra, Ivano Malavolta, Maria Domenica Di Benedetto)
5. [ROUTER: Fog enabled cloud based intelligent resource management approach for smart home IoT devices](#) (Sukhpal Singh Gill, Peter Garraghan, Rajkumar Buyya)
6. [Fine-grained just-in-time defect prediction](#) (Luca Pascarella, Fabio Palomba, Alberto Bacchelli)
7. [Adopting DevOps in the real world: A theory, a model, and a case study](#) (Welder Pinheiro Luz, Gustavo Pinto, Rodrigo Bonifácio)
8. [Energy-aware virtual machine allocation for cloud with resource reservation](#) (Xinqian Zhang, Tingming Wu, Mingsong Chen, Tongquan Wei, Junlong Zhou, Shiyan Hu, Rajkumar Buyya)
9. [Aligning software engineering education with industrial needs: A meta-analysis](#) (Vahid Garousi, Görkem Giray, Eray Tüzün, Cagatay Catal, Michael Felderer)
10. [Software product lines and variability modeling: A tertiary study](#) (Mikko Raatikainen, Juha Tiihonen, Tomi Männistö)

Information and Software Technology 2019

1. [Identifying, categorizing and mitigating threats to validity in software engineering secondary studies](#) (Apostolos Ampatzoglou, Stamatia Bibi, Paris Avgeriou, Marijn Verbeek, Alexander Chatzigeorgiou)
2. [Machine learning techniques for code smell detection: A systematic literature review and meta-analysis](#) (Muhammad Ilyas Azeem, Fabio Palomba, Lin Shi, Qing Wang)
3. [Software defect prediction based on kernel PCA and weighted extreme learning machine](#) (Zhou Xu, Jin Liu, Xiapu Luo, Zijiang Yang, Yifeng Zhang, Peipei Yuan, Yutian Tang, Tao Zhang)
4. [DevOps in practice: A multiple case study of five companies](#) (Lucy Ellen Lwakatare, Terhi Kilamo, Teemu Karvonen, Tanja Sauvola, Ville Heikkilä, Juha Itkonen, Pasi Kuvaja, Tommi Mikkonen, Markku Oivo, Casper Lassenius)
5. [A two-phase transfer learning model for cross-project defect prediction](#) (Chao Liu, Dan Yang, Xin Xia, Meng Yan, Xiaohong Zhang)
6. [A systematic mapping study of infrastructure as code research](#) (Akond Rahman, Rezvan Mahdavi-Hezaveh, Laurie Williams)
7. [Improving defect prediction with deep forest](#) (Tianchi Zhou, Xiaobing Sun, Xin Xia, Bin Li, Xiang Chen)

8. [On the impact of code smells on the energy consumption of mobile applications](#) (Fabio Palomba, Dario Di Nucci, Annibale Panichella, Andy Zaidman, Andrea De Lucia)
9. [Improving bug localization with word embedding and enhanced convolutional neural networks](#) (Yan Xiao, Jacky Keung, Kwabena E. Bennin, Qing Mi)
10. [Automatically identifying code features for software defect prediction: Using AST N-grams](#) (Thomas Shippey, David Bowes, Tracy Hall)

Empirical Software Engineering 2019

1. [Deep code comment generation with hybrid lexical and syntactical information](#) (Xing Hu, Ge Li, Xin Xia, David Lo, Zhi Jin)
2. [How developers engage with static analysis tools in different contexts](#) (Carmine Vassallo, Sebastiano Panichella, Fabio Palomba, Sebastian Proksch, Harald C. Gall, Andy Zaidman)
3. [Towards understanding and detecting fake reviews in app stores](#) (Daniel Martens, Walid Maalej)
4. [The impact of feature reduction techniques on defect prediction models](#) (Masanari Kondo, Cor-Paul Bezemer, Yasutaka Kamei, Ahmed E. Hassan, Osamu Mizuno)
5. [Catalog of energy patterns for mobile applications](#) (Luis Cruz, Rui Abreu)
6. [Mining non-functional requirements from App store reviews](#) (Nishant Jha, Anas Mahmoud)
7. [Gender differences in participation and reward on Stack Overflow](#) (Anna May, Johannes Wachs, Anikó Hannák)
8. [Understanding the motivations, challenges and needs of Blockchain software developers: a survey](#) (Amiangshu Bosu, Anindya Iqbal, Rifat Shahriyar, Partha Chakraborty)
9. [An empirical study of the long duration of continuous integration builds](#) (Taher Ahmed Ghaleb, Daniel Alencar da Costa, Ying Zou)
10. [Selecting fault revealing mutants](#) (Thierry Titchou Chekam, Mike Papadakis, Tegawendé F. Bissyandé, Yves Le Traon, Koushik Sen)

Proceedings of the 2019 27th ACM Joint Meeting on European Software Engineering Conference and Symposium on the Foundations of Software Engineering

1. [Robust log-based anomaly detection on unstable log data](#) (Xu Zhang, Yong Xu, Qingwei Lin, Bo Qiao, Hongyu Zhang, Yingnong Dang, Chunyu Xie, Xinsheng Yang, Qian Cheng, Ze Li, Junjie Chen, Xiaoting He, Randolph Yao, Jian-Guang Lou, Murali Chintalapati, Fura Shen, Dongmei Zhang)

2. [A comprehensive study on deep learning bug characteristics](#) (Md Johirul Islam, Giang Nguyen, Rangeet Pan, Hridesh Rajan)
3. [When deep learning met code search](#) (Jose Cambroner, Hongyu Li, Seohyun Kim, Koushik Sen, Satish Chandra)
4. [Latent error prediction and fault localization for microservice applications by learning from system trace logs](#) (Xiang Zhou, Xin Peng, Tao Xie, Jun Sun, Chao Ji, Dewei Liu, Qilin Xiang, Chuan He)
5. [DeepStellar: model-based quantitative analysis of stateful deep learning systems](#) (Xiaoning Du, Xiaofei Xie, Yi Li, Lei Ma, Yang Liu, Jianjun Zhao)
6. [Black box fairness testing of machine learning models](#) (Aniya Aggarwal, Pranay Lohia, Seema Nagar, Kuntal Dey, Diptikalyan Saha)
7. [Understanding flaky tests: the developer’s perspective](#) (Moritz Eck, Fabio Palomba, Marco Castelluccio, Alberto Bacchelli)
8. [Empirical review of Java program repair tools: a large-scale experiment on 2,141 bugs and 23,551 repair attempts](#) (Thomas Durieux, Fernanda Madeiral, Matias Martinez, Rui Abreu)
9. [iFixFlakies: a framework for automatically fixing order-dependent flaky tests](#) (August Shi, Wing Lam, Reed Oei, Tao Xie, Darko Marinov)
10. [FUDGE: fuzz driver generation at scale](#) (Domagoj Babić, Stefan Bucur, Yaohui Chen, Franjo Ivančić, Tim King, Markus Kusano, Caroline Lemieux, László Szekeres, Wei Wang)

2019 34th IEEE/ACM International Conference on Automated Software Engineering

1. [Manticore: A User-Friendly Symbolic Execution Framework for Binaries and Smart Contracts](#) (Mark Mossberg, Felipe Manzano, Eric Hennenfent, Alex Groce, Gustavo Grieco, Josselin Feist, Trent Brunson, Artem Dinaburg)
2. [Multi-modal Attention Network Learning for Semantic Source Code Retrieval](#) (Yao Wan, Jingdong Shu, Yulei Sui, Guandong Xu, Zhou Zhao, Jian Wu, Philip Yu)
3. [Wuji: Automatic Online Combat Game Testing Using Evolutionary Deep Reinforcement Learning](#) (Yan Zheng, Xiaofei Xie, Ting Su, Lei Ma, Jianye Hao, Zhaopeng Meng, Yang Liu, Ruimin Shen, Yingfeng Chen, Changjie Fan)
4. [Humanoid: A Deep Learning-Based Approach to Automated Black-box Android App Testing](#) (Yuanchun Li, Ziyue Yang, Yao Guo, Xiangqun Chen)
5. [An Empirical Study Towards Characterizing Deep Learning Development and Deployment Across Different Frameworks and Platforms](#) (Qianyu Guo, Sen Chen, Xiaofei Xie, Lei Ma, Qiang Hu, Hongtao Liu, Yang Liu, Jianjun Zhao, Xiaohong Li)

6. [Retrieve and Refine: Exemplar-Based Neural Comment Generation](#) (Bolin Wei)
7. [DIRE: A Neural Approach to Decompiled Identifier Naming](#) (Jeremy Lacomis, Pengcheng Yin, Edward Schwartz, Miltiadis Allamanis, Claire Le Goues, Graham Neubig, Bogdan Vasilescu)
8. [Automatic Generation of Pull Request Descriptions](#) (Zhongxin Liu, Xin Xia, Christoph Treude, David Lo, Shanping Li)
9. [Re-Factoring Based Program Repair Applied to Programming Assignments](#) (Yang Hu, Umair Z. Ahmed, Sergey Mechtaev, Ben Leong, Abhik Roychoudhury)
10. [DeepMutation++: A Mutation Testing Framework for Deep Learning Systems](#) (Qiang Hu, Lei Ma, Xiaofei Xie, Bing Yu, Yang Liu, Jianjun Zhao)

ACM Transactions on Software Engineering and Methodology 2019

1. [An Empirical Study on Learning Bug-Fixing Patches in the Wild via Neural Machine Translation](#) (Michele Tufano, Cody Watson, Gabriele Bavota, Massimiliano Di Penta, Martin White, Denys Poshyvanyk)
2. [RESTful API Automated Test Case Generation with EvoMaster](#) (Andrea Arcuri)
3. [Neural Network-based Detection of Self-Admitted Technical Debt](#) (Xiaoxue Ren, Zhenchang Xing, Xin Xia, David Lo, Xinyu Wang, John Grundy)
4. [Status Quo in Requirements Engineering](#) (Stefan Wagner, Daniel Méndez Fernández, Michael Felderer, Antonio Vetrò, Marcos Kalinowski, Roel Wieringa, Dietmar Pfahl, Tayana Conte, Marie-Therese Christiansson, Desmond Greer, Casper Lassenius, Tomi Männistö, Maleknaz Nayebi, Markku Oivo, Birgit Penzenstadler, Rafael Prikladnicki, Guenther Ruhe, André Schekelmann, Sagar Sen, Rodrigo Spínola, Ahmed Tuzcu, Jose Luis De La Vara, Dietmar Winkler)
5. [Understanding and Analyzing Java Reflection](#) (Yue Li, Tian Tan, Jingling Xue)
6. [Recommending New Features from Mobile App Descriptions](#) (He Jiang, Jingxuan Zhang, Xiaochen Li, Zhilei Ren, David Lo, Xindong Wu, Zhongxuan Luo)
7. [Precise Learn-to-Rank Fault Localization Using Dynamic and Static Features of Target Programs](#) (Yunho Kim, Seokhyeon Mun, Shin Yoo, Moonzoo Kim)
8. [An Active Learning Approach for Improving the Accuracy of Automated Domain Model Extraction](#) (Chetan Arora, Mehrdad Sabetzadeh, Shiva Nejati, Lionel Briand)
9. [Verifying and Quantifying Side-channel Resistance of Masked Software Implementations](#) (Pengfei Gao, Jun Zhang, Fu Song, Chao Wang)
10. [Differential Testing of Certificate Validation in SSL/TLS Implementations](#) (Cong Tian, Chu Chen, Zhenhua Duan, Liang Zhao)

Proceedings of the ACM/IEEE 42nd International Conference on Software Engineering 2020

1. [Empirical review of automated analysis tools on 47,587 Ethereum smart contracts](#) (Thomas Durieux, João F. Ferreira, Rui Abreu, Pedro Cruz)
2. [sFuzz](#) (Tai D. Nguyen, Long H. Pham, Jun Sun, Yun Lin, Quang Tran Minh)
3. [Taxonomy of real faults in deep learning systems](#) (Nargiz Humbatova, Gunel Jahangirova, Gabriele Bavota, Vincenzo Riccio, Andrea Stocco, Paolo Tonella)
4. [DLFix](#) (Yi Li, Shaohua Wang, Tien N. Nguyen)
5. [Retrieval-based neural source code summarization](#) (Jian Zhang, Xu Wang, Hongyu Zhang, Hailong Sun, Xudong Liu)
6. [Big code != big vocabulary](#) (Rafael-Michael Karampatsis, Hlib Babii, Romain Robbes, Charles Sutton, Andrea Janes)
7. [CC2Vec](#) (Thong Hoang, Hong Jin Kang, David Lo, Julia Lawall)
8. [DeepBillboard](#) (Husheng Zhou, Wei Li, Zelun Kong, Junfeng Guo, Yuqun Zhang, Bei Yu, Lingming Zhang, Cong Liu)
9. [Misbehaviour prediction for autonomous driving systems](#) (Andrea Stocco, Michael Weiss, Marco Calzana, Paolo Tonella)
10. [Fuzz testing based data augmentation to improve robustness of deep neural networks](#) (Xiang Gao, Ripon K. Saha, Mukul R. Prasad, Abhik Roychoudhury)

IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering 2020

1. [The Impact of Class Rebalancing Techniques on the Performance and Interpretation of Defect Prediction Models](#) (Chakkrit Tantithamthavorn, Ahmed E. Hassan, Kenichi Matsumoto)
2. [Deep Semantic Feature Learning for Software Defect Prediction](#) (Song Wang, Taiyue Liu, Jaechang Nam, Lin Tan)
3. [ARJA: Automated Repair of Java Programs via Multi-Objective Genetic Programming](#) (Yuan Yuan, Wolfgang Banzhaf)
4. [Smart Greybox Fuzzing](#) (Van-Thuan Pham, Marcel Boehme, Andrew Edward Santosa, Alexandru Razvan Caciulescu, Abhik Roychoudhury)
5. [Machine Learning-Based Prototyping of Graphical User Interfaces for Mobile Apps](#) (Kevin Moran, Carlos Bernal-Cardenas, Michael Curcio, Richard Bonett, Denys Poshyvanyk)
6. [How does Machine Learning Change Software Development Practices?](#) (Zhiyuan Wan, Xin Xia, David Lo, Gail C. Murphy)

7. [Perceptions, Expectations, and Challenges in Defect Prediction](#) (Zhiyuan Wan, Xin Xia, Ahmed E. Hassan, David Lo, Jianwei Yin, Xiaohu Yang)
8. [Finding Faster Configurations Using FLASH](#) (Vivek Nair, Zhe Yu, Tim Menzies, Norbert Siegmund, Sven Apel)
9. [Cognitive Biases in Software Engineering: A Systematic Mapping Study](#) (Rahul Mohanani, Iftaah Salman, Burak Turhan, Pilar Rodriguez, Paul Ralph)
10. [Metamorphic Relations for Enhancing System Understanding and Use](#) (Zhi Quan Zhou, Liqun Sun, Tsong Yueh Chen, Dave Towey)

Journal of Systems and Software 2020

1. [On testing machine learning programs](#) (Housseem Ben Braiek, Foutse Khomh)
2. [A Systematic Mapping Study on Microservices Architecture in DevOps](#) (Muhammad Waseem, Peng Liang, Mojtaba Shahin)
3. [Graph-based root cause analysis for service-oriented and microservice architectures](#) (Álvaro Brandón, Marc Solé, Alberto Huélamo, David Solans, María S. Pérez, Victor Muntés-Mulero)
4. [Software-testing education: A systematic literature mapping](#) (Vahid Garousi, Austen Rainer, Per Lauvås, Andrea Arcuri)
5. [Understanding coordination in global software engineering: A mixed-methods study on the use of meetings and Slack](#) (Viktoria Stray, Nils Brede Moe)
6. [Exploring onboarding success, organizational fit, and turnover intention of software professionals](#) (Gaurav G. Sharma, Klaas-Jan Stol)
7. [When to update systematic literature reviews in software engineering](#) (Emilia Mendes, Claes Wohlin, Katia Felizardo, Marcos Kalinowski)
8. [Systematic literature reviews in software engineering—enhancement of the study selection process using Cohen’s Kappa statistic](#) (Jorge Pérez, Jessica Díaz, Javier Garcia-Martin, Bernardo Tabuenca)
9. [A large empirical assessment of the role of data balancing in machine-learning-based code smell detection](#) (Fabiano Pecorelli, Dario Di Nucci, Coen De Roover, Andrea De Lucia)
10. [CrossRec: Supporting software developers by recommending third-party libraries](#) (Phuong T. Nguyen, Juri Di Rocco, Davide Di Ruscio, Massimiliano Di Penta)

Information and Software Technology 2020

1. [A systematic review of unsupervised learning techniques for software defect prediction](#) (Ning Li, Martin Shepperd, Yuchen Guo)
2. [Large-scale machine learning systems in real-world industrial settings: A review of challenges and solutions](#) (Lucy Ellen Lwakatare, Aiswarya Raj, Ivica Crnkovic, Jan Bosch, Helena Holmström Olsson)
3. [On the performance of hybrid search strategies for systematic literature reviews in software engineering](#) (Erica Mourão, João Felipe Pimentel, Leonardo Murta, Marcos Kalinowski, Emilia Mendes, Claes Wohlin)
4. [Guidelines for the search strategy to update systematic literature reviews in software engineering](#) (Claes Wohlin, Emilia Mendes, Katia Romero Felizardo, Marcos Kalinowski)
5. [A systematic literature review of machine learning techniques for software maintainability prediction](#) (Hadeel Alsolai, Marc Roper)
6. [Ontology-based test generation for automated and autonomous driving functions](#) (Yihao Li, Jianbo Tao, Franz Wotawa)
7. [A systematic literature review on automated log abstraction techniques](#) (Diana El-Masri, Fabio Petrillo, Yann-Gaël Guéhéneuc, Abdelwahab Hamou-Lhadj, Anas Bouziane)
8. [Test Case Prioritization in Continuous Integration environments: A systematic mapping study](#) (Jackson A. Prado Lima, Silvia R. Vergilio)
9. [Intelligent software engineering in the context of agile software development: A systematic literature review](#) (Mirko Perkusich, Lenardo Chaves e Silva, Alexandre Costa, Felipe Ramos, Renata Saraiva, Arthur Freire, Ednaldo Dilorenzo, Emanuel Dantas, Danilo Santos, Kyller Gorgônio, Hyggo Almeida, Angelo Perkusich)
10. [An empirically evaluated checklist for surveys in software engineering](#) (Jefferson Seide Molléri, Kai Petersen, Emilia Mendes)

Empirical Software Engineering 2020

1. [FixMiner: Mining relevant fix patterns for automated program repair](#) (Anil Koyuncu, Kui Liu, Tegawendé F. Bissyandé, Dongsun Kim, Jacques Klein, Martin Monperrus, Yves Le Traon)
2. [Testing machine learning based systems: a systematic mapping](#) (Vincenzo Riccio, Gunel Jahangirova, Andrea Stocco, Nargiz Humbatova, Michael Weiss, Paolo Tonella)
3. [Pandemic programming](#) (Paul Ralph, Sebastian Baltes, Gianisa Adisaputri, Richard Torkar, Vladimir Kovalenko, Marcos Kalinowski, Nicole Novielli, Shin Yoo, Xavier Devroey, Xin Tan, Minghui Zhou, Burak Turhan, Rashina Hoda, Hideaki Hata, Gregorio Robles, Amin Milani Fard, Rana Alkadhi)

4. [An exploratory study of smart contracts in the Ethereum blockchain platform](#) (Gustavo A. Oliva, Ahmed E. Hassan, Zhen Ming Jiang)
5. [A practical guide on conducting eye tracking studies in software engineering](#) (Zohreh Sharafi, Bonita Sharif, Yann-Gaël Guéhéneuc, Andrew Begel, Roman Bednarik, Martha Crosby)
6. [What do Programmers Discuss about Deep Learning Frameworks](#) (Junxiao Han, Emad Shihab, Zhiyuan Wan, Shuiguang Deng, Xin Xia)
7. [The state of adoption and the challenges of systematic variability management in industry](#) (Thorsten Berger, Jan-Philipp Steghöfer, Tewfik Ziadi, Jacques Robin, Jabier Martinez)
8. [The who, what, how of software engineering research: a socio-technical framework](#) (Margaret-Anne Storey, Neil A. Ernst, Courtney Williams, Eirini Kalliamvakou)
9. [Detection, assessment and mitigation of vulnerabilities in open source dependencies](#) (Serena Elisa Ponta, Henrik Plate, Antonino Sabetta)
10. [An empirical characterization of bad practices in continuous integration](#) (Fiorella Zampetti, Carmine Vassallo, Sebastiano Panichella, Gerardo Canfora, Harald Gall, Massimiliano Di Penta)

Proceedings of the 28th ACM Joint Meeting on European Software Engineering Conference and Symposium on the Foundations of Software Engineering 2020

1. [IntelliCode compose: code generation using transformer](#) (Alexey Svyatkovskiy, Shao Kun Deng, Shengyu Fu, Neel Sundaresan)
2. [Harvey: a greybox fuzzer for smart contracts](#) (Valentin Wüstholtz, Maria Christakis)
3. [Is neuron coverage a meaningful measure for testing deep neural networks?](#) (Fabrice Harel-Canada, Lingxiao Wang, Muhammad Ali Gulzar, Quanquan Gu, Miryung Kim)
4. [Object detection for graphical user interface: old fashioned or deep learning or a combination?](#) (Jieshan Chen, Mulong Xie, Zhenchang Xing, Chunyang Chen, Xiwei Xu, Liming Zhu, Guoqiang Li)
5. [Deep learning library testing via effective model generation](#) (Zan Wang, Ming Yan, Junjie Chen, Shuang Liu, Dongdi Zhang)
6. [Model-based exploration of the frontier of behaviours for deep learning system testing](#) (Vincenzo Riccio, Paolo Tonella)
7. [Fairway: a way to build fair ML software](#) (Joymallya Chakraborty, Suvodeep Majumder, Zhe Yu, Tim Menzies)
8. [TypeWriter: neural type prediction with search-based validation](#) (Michael Pradel, Georgios Gousios, Jason Liu, Satish Chandra)

9. [Estimating GPU memory consumption of deep learning models](#) (Yanjie Gao, Yu Liu, Hongyu Zhang, Zhengxian Li, Yonghao Zhu, Haoxiang Lin, Mao Yang)
10. [A comprehensive study on challenges in deploying deep learning based software](#) (Zhenpeng Chen, Yanbin Cao, Yuanqiang Liu, Haoyu Wang, Tao Xie, Xuanzhe Liu)

Proceedings of the 35th IEEE/ACM International Conference on Automated Software Engineering 2020

1. [Multi-task learning based pre-trained language model for code completion](#) (Fang Liu, Ge Li, Yunfei Zhao, Zhi Jin)
2. [SmartBugs](#) (João F. Ferreira, Pedro Cruz, Thomas Durieux, Rui Abreu)
3. [Problems and opportunities in training deep learning software systems](#) (Hung Viet Pham, Shangshu Qian, Jiannan Wang, Thibaud Lutellier, Jonathan Rosenthal, Lin Tan, Yao-liang Yu, Nachiappan Nagappan)
4. [Evaluating representation learning of code changes for predicting patch correctness in program repair](#) (Haoye Tian, Kui Liu, Abdoul Kader Kaboré, Anil Koyuncu, Li Li, Jacques Klein, Tegawendé F. Bissyandé)
5. [Automated patch correctness assessment](#) (Shangwen Wang, Ming Wen, Bo Lin, Hongjun Wu, Yihao Qin, Deqing Zou, Xiaoguang Mao, Hai Jin)
6. [Audee](#) (Qianyu Guo, Xiaofei Xie, Yi Li, Xiaoyu Zhang, Yang Liu, Xiaohong Li, Chao Shen)
7. [Owl eyes](#) (Zhe Liu, Chunyang Chen, Junjie Wang, Yuekai Huang, Jun Hu, Qing Wang)
8. [EXPRESS](#) (Jia Xu, Xiao Liu, Xuejun Li, Lei Zhang, Yun Yang)
9. [Cross-contract static analysis for detecting practical reentrancy vulnerabilities in smart contracts](#) (Yinxing Xue, Mingliang Ma, Yun Lin, Yulei Sui, Jiaming Ye, Tianyong Peng)
10. [Cats are not fish](#) (David Berend, Xiaofei Xie, Lei Ma, Lingjun Zhou, Yang Liu, Chi Xu, Jianjun Zhao)

ACM Transactions on Software Engineering and Methodology 2020

1. [Assessing and Improving Malware Detection Sustainability through App Evolution Studies](#) (Haipeng Cai)
2. [Practical Accuracy Estimation for Efficient Deep Neural Network Testing](#) (Junjie Chen, Zhuo Wu, Zan Wang, Hanmo You, Lingming Zhang, Ming Yan)
3. [Wireframe-based UI Design Search through Image Autoencoder](#) (Jieshan Chen, Chunyang Chen, Zhenchang Xing, Xin Xia, Liming Zhu, John Grundy, Jinshui Wang)
4. [Smart Contract Repair](#) (Xiao Liang Yu, Omar Al-Bataineh, David Lo, Abhik Roychoudhury)

5. [Generating Question Titles for Stack Overflow from Mined Code Snippets](#) (Zhipeng Gao, Xin Xia, John Grundy, David Lo, Yuan-Fang Li)
6. [Predicting Node Failures in an Ultra-Large-Scale Cloud Computing Platform](#) (Yangguang Li, Zhen Ming (Jack) Jiang, Heng Li, Ahmed E. Hassan, Cheng He, Ruirui Huang, Zhengda Zeng, Mian Wang, Pinan Chen)
7. [Monotone Precision and Recall Measures for Comparing Executions and Specifications of Dynamic Systems](#) (Artem Polyvyanyy, Andreas Solti, Matthias Weidlich, Claudio Di Ciccio, Jan Mendling)
8. [Modular Tree Network for Source Code Representation Learning](#) (Wenhan Wang, Ge Li, Sijie Shen, Xin Xia, Zhi Jin)
9. [Visualizing Distributed System Executions](#) (Ivan Beschastnikh, Perry Liu, Albert Xing, Patty Wang, Yuriy Brun, Michael D. Ernst)
10. [Handling SQL Databases in Automated System Test Generation](#) (Andrea Arcuri, Juan P. Galeotti)

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1. [CURE: Code-Aware Neural Machine Translation for Automatic Program Repair](#) (Nan Jiang, Thibaud Lutellier, Lin Tan)
2. [Code Prediction by Feeding Trees to Transformers](#) (Seohyun Kim, Jinman Zhao, Yuchi Tian, Satish Chandra)
3. [Studying the Usage of Text-To-Text Transfer Transformer to Support Code-Related Tasks](#) (Antonio Mastropaolo, Simone Scalabrino, Nathan Cooper, David Nader Palacio, Denys Poshyvanyk, Rocco Oliveto, Gabriele Bavota)
4. [Semi-Supervised Log-Based Anomaly Detection via Probabilistic Label Estimation](#) (Lin Yang, Junjie Chen, Zan Wang, Weijing Wang, Jiajun Jiang, Xuyuan Dong, Wenbin Zhang)
5. [Towards Automating Code Review Activities](#) (Rosalia Tufano, Luca Pascarella, Michele Tufano, Denys Poshyvanyk, Gabriele Bavota)
6. [Fault Localization with Code Coverage Representation Learning](#) (Yi Li, Shaohua Wang, Tien Nguyen)
7. [InferCode: Self-Supervised Learning of Code Representations by Predicting Subtrees](#) (Nghì D. Q. Bui, Yijun Yu, Lingxiao Jiang)
8. [Traceability Transformed: Generating More Accurate Links with Pre-Trained BERT Models](#) (Jinfeng Lin, Yalin Liu, Qingkai Zeng, Meng Jiang, Jane Cleland-Huang)
9. [Prioritizing Test Inputs for Deep Neural Networks via Mutation Analysis](#) (Zan Wang, Hanmo You, Junjie Chen, Yingyi Zhang, Xuyuan Dong, Wenbin Zhang)

10. ["How Was Your Weekend?" Software Development Teams Working From Home During COVID-19](#) (Courtney Miller, Paige Rodeghero, Margaret-Anne Storey, Denae Ford, Thomas Zimmermann)

IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering 2021

1. [Smart Contract Development: Challenges and Opportunities](#) (Weiqin Zou, David Lo, Pavneet Singh Kochhar, Xuan-Bach Dinh Le, Xin Xia, Yang Feng, Zhenyu Chen, Baowen Xu)
2. [The Art, Science, and Engineering of Fuzzing: A Survey](#) (Valentin J.M. Manes, HyungSeok Han, Choongwoo Han, Sang Kil Cha, Manuel Egele, Edward J. Schwartz, Maverick Woo)
3. [SEQUENCER: Sequence-to-Sequence Learning for End-to-End Program Repair](#) (Zimin Chen, Steve James Kommrusch, Michele Tufano, Louis-Noel Pouchet, Denys Poshyvanyk, Martin Monperrus)
4. [Fault Analysis and Debugging of Microservice Systems: Industrial Survey, Benchmark System, and Empirical Study](#) (Xiang Zhou, Xin Peng, Tao Xie, Jun Sun, Chao Ji, Wenhai Li, Dan Ding)
5. [An Empirical Study of Fault Localization Families and Their Combinations](#) (Daming Zou, Jingjing Liang, Yingfei Xiong, Michael D. Ernst, Lu Zhang)
6. [Automatic Feature Learning for Predicting Vulnerable Software Components](#) (Hoa Khanh Dam, Truyen Tran, Trang Pham, Shien Wee Ng, John Grundy, Aditya Ghose)
7. [Beyond Technical Aspects: How Do Community Smells Influence the Intensity of Code Smells?](#) (Fabio Palomba, Damian Andrew Tamburri, Francesca Arcelli Fontana, Rocco Oliveto, Andy Zaidman, Alexander Serebrenik)
8. [Mining Fix Patterns for FindBugs Violations](#) (Kui Liu, Dongsun Kim, Tegawende F. Bissyande, Shin Yoo, Yves Le Traon)
9. [Service Candidate Identification from Monolithic Systems Based on Execution Traces](#) (Wuxia Jin, Ting Liu, Yuanfang Cai, Rick Kazman, Ran Mo, Qinghua Zheng)
10. [Deep Learning Based Code Smell Detection](#) (Hui Liu, Jiahao Jin, Zhifeng Xu, Yifan Bu, Yanzhen Zou, Lu Zhang)

Journal of Systems and Software 2021

1. [A systematic literature review of blockchain and smart contract development: Techniques, tools, and open challenges](#) (Anna Vacca, Andrea Di Sorbo, Corrado A. Visaggio, Gerardo Canfora)
2. [Requirements engineering challenges and practices in large-scale agile system development](#) (Rashidah Kasauli, Eric Knauss, Jennifer Horkoff, Grischa Liebel, Francisco Gomes de Oliveira Neto)

3. [A software engineering perspective on engineering machine learning systems: State of the art and challenges](#) (Görkem Giray)
4. [Exploring the intersection between software industry and Software Engineering education - A systematic mapping of Software Engineering Trends](#) (Orges Cico, Letizia Jaccheri, Anh Nguyen-Duc, He Zhang)
5. [A systematic literature review on Technical Debt prioritization: Strategies, processes, factors, and tools](#) (Valentina Lenarduzzi, Terese Besker, Davide Taibi, Antonio Martini, Francesca Arcelli Fontana)
6. [Design, monitoring, and testing of microservices systems: The practitioners' perspective](#) (Muhammad Waseem, Peng Liang, Mojtaba Shahin, Amleto Di Salle, Gastón Márquez)
7. [Learning software configuration spaces: A systematic literature review](#) (Juliana Alves Pereira, Mathieu Acher, Hugo Martin, Jean-Marc Jézéquel, Goetz Botterweck, Anthony Ventresque)
8. [Code smell detection by deep direct-learning and transfer-learning](#) (Tushar Sharma, Vasiliki Efstathiou, Panos Louridas, Diomidis Spinellis)
9. [A critical review on the evaluation of automated program repair systems](#) (Kui Liu, Li Li, Anil Koyuncu, Dongsun Kim, Zhe Liu, Jacques Klein, Tegawendé F. Bissyandé)
10. [A ground-truth dataset and classification model for detecting bots in GitHub issue and PR comments](#) (Mehdi Golzadeh, Alexandre Decan, Damien Legay, Tom Mens)

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1. [Automation of systematic literature reviews: A systematic literature review](#) (Raymon van Dinter, Bedir Tekinerdogan, Cagatay Catal)
2. [BGNN4VD: Constructing Bidirectional Graph Neural-Network for Vulnerability Detection](#) (Sicong Cao, Xiaobing Sun, Lili Bo, Ying Wei, Bin Li)
3. [Understanding and addressing quality attributes of microservices architecture: A Systematic literature review](#) (Shanshan Li, He Zhang, Zijia Jia, Chenxing Zhong, Cheng Zhang, Zhihao Shan, Jinfeng Shen, Muhammad Ali Babar)
4. [A risk prediction model for software project management based on similarity analysis of context histories](#) (Alexsandro Souza Filippetto, Robson Lima, Jorge Luis Victória Barbosa)
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6. [From monolithic systems to Microservices: An assessment framework](#) (Florian Auer, Valentina Lenarduzzi, Michael Felderer, Davide Taibi)

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1. [A syntax-guided edit decoder for neural program repair](#) (Qihao Zhu, Zeyu Sun, Yuan-an Xiao, Wenjie Zhang, Kang Yuan, Yingfei Xiong, Lu Zhang)
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7. [A comprehensive study of deep learning compiler bugs](#) (Qingchao Shen, Haoyang Ma, Junjie Chen, Yongqiang Tian, Shing-Chi Cheung, Xiang Chen)
8. [Reassessing automatic evaluation metrics for code summarization tasks](#) (Devjeet Roy, Sarah Fakhoury, Venera Arnaoudova)
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1. [Log-based Anomaly Detection Without Log Parsing](#) (Van-Hoang Le, Hongyu Zhang)
2. [SMARTIAN: Enhancing Smart Contract Fuzzing with Static and Dynamic Data-Flow Analyses](#) (Jaeseung Choi, Doyeon Kim, Soomin Kim, Gustavo Grieco, Alex Groce, Sang Kil Cha)
3. [What do pre-trained code models know about code?](#) (Anjan Karmakar, Romain Robbes)
4. [Finding A Needle in a Haystack: Automated Mining of Silent Vulnerability Fixes](#) (Jiayuan Zhou, Michael Pacheco, Zhiyuan Wan, Xin Xia, David Lo, Yuan Wang, Ahmed E. Hassan)
5. [EditSum: A Retrieve-and-Edit Framework for Source Code Summarization](#) (Jia Allen Li, Yongmin Li, Ge Li, Xing Hu, Xin Xia, Zhi Jin)

6. [Groot: An Event-graph-based Approach for Root Cause Analysis in Industrial Settings](#) (Hanzhang Wang, Zhengkai Wu, Huai Jiang, Yichao Huang, Jiamu Wang, Selcuk Kopru, Tao Xie)
7. [On Multi-Modal Learning of Editing Source Code](#) (Saikat Chakraborty, Baishakhi Ray)
8. [PyExplainer: Explaining the Predictions of Just-In-Time Defect Models](#) (Chanathip Pornprasit, Chakkrit Tantithamthavorn, Jirayus Jiarpakdee, Michael Fu, Patanamon Thongtanunam)
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5. [NatGen: generative pre-training by “naturalizing” source code](#) (Saikat Chakraborty, Toufique Ahmed, Yangruibo Ding, Premkumar T. Devanbu, Baishakhi Ray)
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1. [Few-shot training LLMs for project-specific code-summarization](#) (Toufique Ahmed, Premkumar Devanbu)
2. [CoditT5: Pretraining for Source Code and Natural Language Editing](#) (Jiyang Zhang, Sheena Panthaplackel, Pengyu Nie, Junyi Jessy Li, Milos Gligoric)
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2. [In-IDE Code Generation from Natural Language: Promise and Challenges](#) (Frank F. Xu, Bogdan Vasilescu, Graham Neubig)
3. [A Systematic Literature Review on the Use of Deep Learning in Software Engineering Research](#) (Cody Watson, Nathan Cooper, David Nader Palacio, Kevin Moran, Denys Poshyvanyk)
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10. [Adversarial Robustness of Deep Code Comment Generation](#) (Yu Zhou, Xiaoqing Zhang, Juanjuan Shen, Tingting Han, Taolue Chen, Harald Gall)

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